

DISSERTATION
Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Degree of
Doctor of Business Administration

Presented to the
Swiss School of Management

Lean Philosophy Impact on Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability

by

Karim Albendary

Supervisor: Dr. Amr Sukkar

Panel Member: Dr. Ahmed Sobhi

Panel Member: Dr. Hamdy Elwany

Panel Member: Dr. Vasileios Margaritis

October 2024

Abstract

Challenges faced by the healthcare supply chains have brought the importance of efficient healthcare systems that reduce costs and improve service delivery to the forefront. Lean Philosophy (Lean) has been applicable to different industries. However, healthcare has different characteristics that need a custom-fit solution. This dissertation on Lean applications in healthcare examines standardized implementation throughout supply chains to improve operations management and patient care. In terms of methodology, a quantitative analysis was performed using surveys from 39 healthcare practitioners from 21 hospitals in Saudi Arabia. Data were analyzed using SPSS for descriptive and inferential statistics to test the impact of Lean and to test if the reduction of inventory waste acts as a mediator between Lean and supply chain profitability. Lean integration had strong impacts on supply chain efficiency while also having a positive effect on lowering operational costs and improving patient outcomes, all of which contribute to profitability. The research found a so-called scalable Lean model applicable in different healthcare contexts that can achieve comparable profitability increases.

Keywords: lean Philosophy - Healthcare Industry - Supply Chain Management - Inventory Waste – Profitability

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank God for the blessings and guidance He has provided to me over the time I have been carrying out this research project. His presence has been a source of strength and inspiration. I extend my heartfelt thanks to Dr. Amr Sukkar for his exceptional supervision and guidance during the research period. His insights and advice were invaluable. I am profoundly grateful to Dr. Ayman S. Anwar for his unwavering support and valuable contribution to the statistical analysis. His expertise was crucial to the success of this project. My sincere thanks also go to my company, Magrabi Hospitals and Centers, and its leaders, Dr. Abdulrahman Barzangi and Mr. Mutasim Ali Reza, for their indispensable support. Their commitment to enhancing supply chain practices in healthcare has been a driving force behind this research. Finally, I would like to thank my family for their unwavering support, which was instrumental in the success of this project.

Contents

DISSERTATION.....	1
Abstract.....	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
1.1 Introduction / Research Problem	8
1.2. Research Gap and Objectives.....	10
1.2.1 Research Gap.....	10
1.2.2 Research Objectives	10
1.3. Research Questions.....	11
1.4 Research hypothesis/assumption.....	11
1.5. The scope of research (Delimitations).....	11
1.6. Research philosophy, approach, and technique.	12
1.7. Significance of Study	12
CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Key Concepts and Principles of SCM and Lean Philosophy.....	18
Control Charts.....	23
Pareto Analysis	24
Root Cause Analysis.....	25
DMAIC & PDCA	25
5S (sort, straighten, shine, standardize, and sustain):	27
2.3 Lean impact on supply chain efficiency.....	28
2.4 Lean Philosophy Application in Healthcare Supply Chain Management	31
2.5 Potential Benefits Of Lean on Profitability	35
2.6 Lean Impact On Patient Outcomes.....	39
2.7 Lean Philosophy Implementation Challenges.....	41
2.8 Lean Philosophy Implementation Limitations.....	45
2.9 Tailored Approaches and Strategies.....	47
2.10 Future Directions and Recommendations.....	48
2.11 Conclusion	52
CHAPTER III: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND.....	61
3.1 Theoretical Framework.....	61
3.2 Conceptual Framework	61

3.3 Key Constructs.....	62
3.4 Definition of Terms.....	63
3.5 Detailed Explanation Using Key Constructs.....	66
3.6 Integration of Research Questions and Survey Results.....	67
CHAPTER IV: METHODS AND PROCEDURES	69
4.1 Research Design.....	69
4.2 Data Gathering Procedure.....	69
4.3 Data Analysis Guide	69
4.4.1 Scope:.....	74
4.4.2 Limitations:.....	74
4.5 Significance of the Study	75
4.6 Conclusion	76
CHAPTER V: DATA PRESENTATION.....	77
5.1 Descriptive Statistics.....	77
5.2 Inferential Statistics.....	85
5.3 Conclusion	88
CHAPTER VI: FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS.....	90
6.1 Specific Findings.....	90
6.2 Hypothesis	91
6.3 Conclusion	92
CHAPTER VII: RECOMMENDATIONS.....	93
7.1 Introduction	93
7.1.1 Emphasize Training and Education	93
7.1.2 Foster a Culture of Continuous Improvement	94
7.1.3 Integrate Lean Tools with Existing Processes	94
7.1.4 Address Barriers to Lean Implementation	94
7.1.5 Enhance Collaboration Across Departments	95
7.1.6 Focus on Patient-Centered Care	95
7.2 Conclusion	96
CHAPTER VIII: SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS.....	97
8.1 Introduction	97
8.2 Summary of Key Findings	97
8.3 Rereading the Research Aims	97
8.4 Implications for Healthcare Sector	97

8.5 Future Research Directions	98
8.6 Conclusion	99
REFERENCES.....	101
Appendices.....	110
A. Lean Philosophy Impact on Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability Survey	110
Survey Questions Instructions.....	112
Survey Questions	113

Table of Figures

Table 1: Type of wastes in Healthcare – Source (Fiorillo et al., 2021).....	21
Table 2: Priority of sub-criteria for leanness in the healthcare delivery system – Source (Bharsakade et al., 2021)	23
Table 3: Cycle view of the developed framework – Source (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022)	58
Table 4:Survey Questions Mapping with Lean Application Dimension, Research variables & questions.	73
Table 5: Case Processing Summary	79
Table 6: Descriptives.....	82
Table 7: Tests of Normality.....	83
Table 8:Correlation Analysis	87
Table 9: T-test	88
Figure 1: Internal supply chain of a hospital. Source: (Borges et al., 2020).....	14
Figure 2: XmR chart of bed wait times – Source (Arthur, 2016)	24
Figure 3: Pareto chart of reported problems – Source (Pyzdek, 2021)	24
Figure 4: Structure of cause and effect diagram – Source (Pyzdek, 2021).....	25
Figure 5: PDCA improvement cycle – Source (Pyzdek, 2021).....	26
Figure 6:Conceptual Framework	62
Figure 7Conceptual Framework Linked to Theoretical Framework	66
Figure 8: Respondent Age	78
Figure 9: Respondent Gender	78
Figure 10 Responders years of experience.....	79
Figure 11: Staff Commitment to Lean Philosophy	84
Figure 12: Leadership Commitment to Lean.....	84
Figure 13: Continuous Improvement Model	85
Figure 14:Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	85

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction / Research Problem

Recently, maintaining patient care quality while dealing with the financial and operational demands of running efficient services has brought about increasing difficulties for the healthcare industry. A major area of concern in these difficulties concerns the healthcare supply chain, which is a multifaceted system that includes purchasing decisions and logistics management crucial for providing prompt and efficient patient care. In contrast, to sectors that have predictable supply chains the healthcare industry deals with complex and ever changing supply chains that are characterized by varying demands and urgent requirements while needing to comply with strict regulatory guidelines. Due to these challenges, in the healthcare sector, traditional supply chain management methods are inadequate, highlighting the importance of solutions that can efficiently handle resources, reduce waste, and enhance overall operations efficiency.

The Lean Philosophy originated from the Toyota Production System. It focuses on reducing waste and enhancing value through processes and continuous improvement efforts in various industries like the manufacturing and logistics sectors. However, the healthcare sector's implementation of principles in supply chain management remains an area that requires exploration for its potential benefits. This research focused on filling this void by exploring how Lean Philosophy can be tailored and utilized in healthcare supply chains to improve effectiveness and boost success while taking into account the distinct obstacles specific, to healthcare, like varying patient requirements and the critical importance of quality assurance alongside the intricate connections, among various departments and individuals involved.

Lean principles play a role in healthcare supply chains by not only cutting costs but also improving service delivery for better patient care quality, according to research findings in the field of healthcare operations management. Inefficiencies, like inventory and long wait times, can burden institutions with operational costs and resource strains that impact their long-term viability. This research further developed these ideas by examining inventory waste as a link between implementing practices and the overall profitability of the supply chain in healthcare settings, highlighting the importance of inventory management in reducing costs and improving operational flexibility.

In this study, the context of Saudi Arabia as the area of interest appears intriguing for investigating how Lean Philosophy can be implemented in managing healthcare supply chains there. The Saudi Arabian healthcare system has undergone modernization efforts to enhance infrastructure and service delivery as part of national development initiatives. Despite these advancements, in the healthcare sector aimed at improving services and facilities country, like other global health systems, challenges remain, including escalating operational expenses, meeting increasing patient demands, and efficiently allocating resources without compromising care standards. The study carried out in this situation offers insights that may be applicable to healthcare systems in areas as well, especially those in developing regions dealing with comparable logistical and financial obstacles.

The study's methodology included gathering information from 39 healthcare professionals in 21 hospitals in Saudi Arabia and examining it through an online survey. A thorough analysis was conducted using SPSS, which enabled the recognition of trends and validation of assumptions regarding Lean's influence on enhancing supply chain effectiveness. This real-world data adds to what we know by offering a framework grounded in evidence for applying principles in healthcare environments.

This research delved into examples of applying practices in healthcare settings rather than just discussing theories conceptually from a distance. It examines how certain Lean techniques, like mapping out value streams and implementing Just In Time (JIT) inventory management and continuous flow concepts, can be customized to improve the complexities of managing healthcare logistics. These methodologies assist in pinpointing tasks and optimizing workflows to allocate resources efficiently and meet requirements promptly. The research illustrated how Lean practices can significantly influence supply chain measurements in the healthcare sector – making an argument for healthcare institutions to integrate Lean methodologies into their strategic plans to manage costs and enhance quality standards.

Furthermore, the research highlighted the impact of implementing principles in healthcare settings by exploring how they shape the organizational culture there. The results indicate that Lean methodologies not only enhance performance but also promote a culture of ongoing enhancement and teamwork in addressing challenges. This shift in culture is crucial for

maintaining lasting advantages and integrating improvements into routines.

The research highlighted the importance of Lean Philosophy in improving healthcare supply chain management. By reducing inventory waste, organizations can enhance profits and service quality. The study introduced a model for healthcare leaders and policymakers to boost efficiency and financial stability. Overall, it provided strong evidence for implementing Lean practices as a key element of modern healthcare administration.

1.2. Research Gap and Objectives

1.2.1 Research Gap

While extensive literature exists on specific practices and improvements of the supply chain, there still exists the need to give greater importance to the lean philosophy aimed at enhancing healthcare performance. The study sought to fill the existing gap in the research. The above discussion comprehensively discusses lean supply chain management in healthcare service operations based on theoretical and practical viewpoints.

LSCM in healthcare is relatively unexplored as the practice is still in its infancy; accordingly, the absence of studies on the topic has been acknowledged. The general objective of implementing LSCM in healthcare, as explained above, is to eliminate the waste pertaining to non-value creation activities such as waiting, overproduction, unnecessary movement, transportation, unnecessary processing, stocks, and underutilization of employees, which are expensive and challenging in the context of healthcare delivery. (Khorasani et al., 2020).

Since profitability refers to the enterprise's operating efficiency and the enterprise's ability to get a sufficient return on the capital and employees used in the business operation, The research aimed to increase healthcare supply chain profitability. The study investigated the impact of Lean Philosophy on Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability through mediating inventory waste reduction.

1.2.2 Research Objectives

The main objective of the research is to evaluate the impact of Lean Philosophy on the profitability of healthcare supply chains by assessing how inventory waste reduction serves as a

mediating factor. The study aims to:

- Analyze the effectiveness of Lean Philosophy in improving operational efficiency and profitability in healthcare supply chains.
- Identify key strategies within Lean applications that contribute to inventory management optimization.
- Provide actionable insights for healthcare institutions on how to integrate Lean methodologies effectively to maximize financial outcomes.

1.3. Research Questions

- Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?
- Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
- Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?

1.4 Research hypothesis/assumption

- Hypothesis H₁: Lean philosophy positively impacts healthcare supply Chain profitability.
- Hypothesis H₀: Lean philosophy does not impact healthcare supply Chain profitability.
- Hypothesis H₂: Inventory Optimization positively impacts Supply chain profitability.
- Hypothesis H_{0_2}: Inventory Optimization has no impact on Supply chain profitability.
- Hypothesis H₃: Lean Philosophy has a positive impact on inventory optimization.
- Hypothesis H_{0_3}: Lean Philosophy has no impact on inventory optimization.

1.5. The scope of research (Delimitations)

The research investigates the impact of lean philosophy on healthcare organizations and the obstacles they encounter while enhancing their supply chains. The study centers on the theoretical integration of lean philosophy in inventory management procedures within the

healthcare sector and how it can influence financial outcomes. An online survey was used to analyze lean applications in hospitals in Saudi Arabia.

1.6. Research philosophy, approach, and technique.

The study involves collecting data from the healthcare industry in Saudi Arabia and evaluating the impact of implementing a lean philosophy on supply chain profitability, with an emphasis on reducing inventory waste. The research used a quantitative approach, utilizing a survey questionnaire to gather data for descriptive, explanatory, causal, and analytical analysis. A convenient cluster sampling method was employed, and hypothesis testing was conducted using SPSS.

The research approach for this study was a systematic review of the literature, followed by feedback from healthcare practitioners in order to establish the gaps in the current healthcare system. Academic research engines such as Academia, Google Scholar, EBSCOhost, Egyptian Knowledge Bank, and Emerald Insight, as well as AI research engines like Elicit and Consensus, were used in this search.

This applied research used the positivism philosophy to apply Lean theories in the healthcare supply chain organization. It will refer to practical results from a Survey using quantitative methods and a deductive approach. The study discussed the supply chain metrics that improved after adopting the lean philosophy, including inventory turnover rate and profitability.

1.7. Significance of Study

In this research, the study aimed to explore the changeable impact of Lean Philosophy on the efficiency of healthcare supply chains. This area has, until now, been the least explored area in Lean research. While it is firmly established in domains like the automotive and manufacturing ones, the lean philosophy remains largely nonutilized in healthcare. The study aimed to bridge that gap by deploying lean principles to healthcare, which is one of the most intricate operational domains where many variables are uncertain and high-quality delivery in a patient-oriented manner is imperative. The outcomes of the research gave visionary perspectives in ascertaining the delivery of healthcare in the light of enhancing efficiency through lean practices that lead to better patient outcomes. The research characterized itself by

systematically applying Lean methods to healthcare supply chains and, more dramatically, making the case for increasing profits by cutting down on inventory waste and improving supply chain performance.

The study explained the critical need for Lean adaptations to address the particularity of healthcare, such as the need to control costs while taking into consideration the quality of the delivered healthcare and the nature of complicated logistics and demand variability. Unlike the traditional applications in which Lean is aimed at minimizing waste and standardizing activities, this research modified Lean with an eye on the healthcare environment exclusively.

The study also explored the relevance of Saudi healthcare in today's globalized world and argued that the needs that existed previously in the region still exist in the recent era of globalization. As in many healthcare systems around the world, Saudi Arabia was faced with increasing costs, an increase in patient expectations and demand, and other issues and challenges for the provision of comprehensive care. With such regional emphasis, the research showed a framework that was possible for other health systems, particularly those in developing countries, which demonstrated that Lean was able to be employed in a framework with different but challenging logistics, financial, and cultural characteristics. The positive outcomes of the Lean applications in Saudi hospitals also provided compelling evidence for other health systems, presenting a case in which free reforms based on Lean approaches, which emphasize waste elimination, efficiency, and quality, could be adopted across systems.

In summary, this study makes a compelling case for the adoption of Lean Philosophy principles in the management of healthcare-related supply chains. It provides an evidence-based and universalizable approach. It provides a basis for more research and wider application by systematically explaining the different dimensions of Lean on healthcare supply chains. Not only does this research make a contribution to the practice of healthcare supply chain management, by closing the circle between Lean theory and applications in practice, this research also advances the area of healthcare intelligence.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The healthcare supply chain (HCSC) plays an important role in the healthcare industry, contributing greatly to its overall operations. The healthcare industry is a particular industry that includes the provision of both goods and services: pharmaceutical and medical equipment, disposables and waste, information technology, food and beverage, transportation, and laundry services. While these products and services are developed and delivered with safety as the top priority, they often encounter difficulties with ordering, dispatching, and utilization. Despite these challenges, the global healthcare economy continues to grow. Nevertheless, issues such as healthcare accessibility and complexity still persist on a global scale. (Hossain & Thakur, 2020)

Patients play an active role in seeking healthcare services within healthcare organizations; as stated by Borges et al. (2020), the healthcare supply chain is known for its complexity, especially within hospitals where the cost of operating a multi-activity supply chain can be inefficient. To manage this complexity, healthcare supply chains can be divided into two approaches: Tenets internal and external (as represented in Figure 1 below). The internal approach is directed at the internal functioning of the hospital, while the external approach is connected with the suppliers. While most authors focus on the internal supply chain perspective, general investigations have only addressed particular levels of a department.

Figure 1: Internal supply chain of a hospital. Source: (Borges et al., 2020)

Previous studies have primarily concentrated on establishing lean principles within the healthcare supply chain. These investigations have emphasized the significance of implementing best practices and have pinpointed areas for enhancing performance and implementation.

In the fast-paced global marketplace today, Lean SCM has become a popular strategy for businesses seeking to balance cost-effectiveness and customer demands. This approach enables companies to identify innovative supply chain methods, enhance profitability, and improve overall performance. By fostering collaborative partnerships with customers and remaining responsive to their needs, businesses can effectively satisfy demands and drive greater satisfaction.(Basal & Sarkbay, 2023)

Healthcare providers need help in meeting patient needs due to complex supply chain management. A shortage of qualified personnel and inefficient practices compound these challenges. Furthermore, there is also the need to develop more organizational competencies in delivering business strategies that could address the issue of supply-side cost and also to increase availability and access to affordable and timely healthcare as demand continues to rise as well as to manage the supply chain logistics in order to contain the operating cost of healthcare (Adebanjo et al., 2016) .

Mahmoud et al. (2021) define Lean Management as a concept that encourages the organization to enhance value-adding activities and eliminate anything unnecessary or wasteful, which can include overproduction, unnecessary steps, overburden, or delay. It is also regarded as a remedy for waste in organizations. Waste is any activity that does not add any value but rather utilizes organizational resources and, therefore, results in ineffectiveness, inflexibility, and unnecessary expense. Sonali et al. (2022) state that lean production originated in the Japanese car industry. Meanwhile, American cars were known for high maintenance requirements in the 1970s. The Toyota Production System (TPS) altered the field by providing dependability on relatively cheaper automobiles. This development led manufacturers and academics to head to Japan to learn about the concepts now associated with lean production. Lean means less than mass production with less human effort in factories, less space occupied by manufacturing, less invested in tools and hours spent on engineering, and finally, half the time to design new models. Lean production is an approach that aims to minimize waste and increase efficiency. The

methodology has five stages: recognizing customer value, analyzing inefficiencies, creating uninterrupted flow, establishing flow based on demand, and expediting improvement. Managers use Lean to eliminate wasteful processes that don't add value, such as idle waiting and Inventory.

According to Yaduvanshi and Sharma (2017) research, Lean methodology in healthcare focuses on eliminating waste to deliver better value for patients and stakeholders. Hospitals must embrace a lean thinking culture to succeed and involve all staff in process redesign. Unlike other models, lean methodology prioritizes waste elimination before delivering products or services. Organizations can improve product quality and reduce waste by standardizing processes and using Six Sigma. The Toronto Hospital for Sick Children saved \$140,000 over four years by addressing inefficiencies in its supply chain and establishing new control limits on inventory.

According to Narayanan et al. (2022) hospitals have been able to opt for lean revenues and hence make more revenues. Contrary to what we have seen in other industries, only 53 % of healthcare organizations employ inventory management software or models because of the constraints that arise within the healthcare industry, thereby giving priority to supply availability rather than efficiency. Past research has explored various ways of reducing costs in the healthcare supply chain. All these investigations suggest that reducing the number of products and the reduction in business partners such as suppliers and SCM facilities make it possible to cut SCM costs. They have also realized that with the help of CPFR and VMI processes, accuracy in linking healthcare supply and reducing inventory expenses are made easier (Essila, 2022).

According to Uddin et al. (2023) indicates that supply chain management can influence profits and operational efficiency by reducing inventory and lead times, holding costs, and speeding up order fulfillment. As a result, sales and income can be boosted. Moreover, a streamlined supply chain allows a business to adapt to market shifts, increasing flexibility swiftly. Siagian and Tarigan (2021) explain that vendor-managed inventory systems can improve a company's performance by allowing vendors to manage raw materials and components needed for manufacturing, eliminating the need for businesses to maintain inventory and ensuring timely delivery of urgent materials. Studies have shown that this system can boost performance.

Integrating both philosophy and tools is necessary for successful lean practices. Some organizations prioritize only tools, leading to poor long-term outcomes. It can be hard to

distinguish between full embracement and tool-only use. Lean philosophy includes four key aspects: a commitment to constant improvement, multiple methods and tools, a focus on empowering employees, and cultural transformations to reduce waste across the value chain. Practical lean tools rely on enhancing the flow of information, removing departmental barriers, and ensuring that the flow of patients in the healthcare system is efficient (Akmal et al., 2020).

Although there has been extensive research on SC performance and lean practices, the healthcare industry still needs more development in the concept of a thin supply chain and its evaluation. This is due to a paucity of research on this industry, as well as deficiencies in performance evaluation approaches (Adebanjo et al., 2016). Implementing lean methodologies in healthcare relies on the human factor more than in other service industries or manufacturing. Given the extensive involvement of patients and the collaborative nature of healthcare providers and patients, along with the intricate and unpredictable hospital environment, actively and intentionally engaging in the lean implementation process is vital for success. (Narayanan et al., 2022)

In a research conducted by Suman and Prajapati (2021), it was concluded that the it may be challenging to implement the Lean & Six Sigma due to "lack of knowledge" and "availability of resources." According to a recent study, adopting the Lean Six Sigma methodology in KSA is still nascent, and many initiatives that are in place primarily focus on improving Length of Stay, Waiting Time, Discharge Time, Cycle Time, and Process Enhancement. Akmal et al., (2020) pointed out a lack of linkages made to lean tools in the context of healthcare supply chain and underscored the importance of taking into consideration the supply chain management to ensure that inventory management and supplier relations among other lean tools could be optimally utilized across the supply networks. This move away from functional silos and recognition of the need to map the patient journey as a more complex value chain requires a systemic approach to enable value co-creation by clinicians, patients/families, funders, and the community.

The impact of the Lean management system still needs to be more conclusive. Although small-scale studies have shown positive results in hospital units/departments, publication bias may be a factor. Existing literature has revealed that the adoption of lean management in hospitals contributes to improved performance measures like waste reduction, increased

emergency department throughput, and lower expenditures. Lean adoption is also linked to higher financial performance and fewer patients missing services in the emergency department. Hospitals using Lean techniques in multiple units have lower expenses per patient discharge, fewer readmissions, less imaging use, and higher patient experience scores. Lean implementation primarily improves efficiency and financial viability measures, but it can also enhance patient experience by prioritizing customer feedback and empowering frontline staff to address patients' needs and preferences. (Shortell et al., 2021)

A literature review was predominantly undertaken during September and October of 2023. Further exploration occurred throughout November and December of 2023, utilizing various academic research tools such as Academia, Google Scholar, Emerald, and the Egyptian Knowledge Bank. Additionally, new AI research tools, including Elicit and Consensus, will be incorporated into the research process.

2.2 Key Concepts and Principles of SCM and Lean Philosophy

SCM coordinates the materials, information, and money flow from suppliers to consumers. It involves all processes and procedures of an organization and ensures products and services move from their place of origin to where they are used. SCM can increase productivity, customer satisfaction, and profitability. The effectiveness of a supply chain is paramount when it comes to managing it properly and reflects the efficiency of the SC in meeting the needs of customers while also maintaining cost efficiency, adaptability, and responsiveness. This evaluation holds immense significance in highly competitive markets where there is a growing demand for timely delivery and quality services. This proportionately contributes to the profitability of businesses (Uddin et al., 2023).

Arthur (2016) has succinctly condensed lean methodology principles into five key concepts universally applicable to all industries, such as manufacturing, healthcare, and administration. These are five fundamental principles to improve your product or service. First, allow the patient to pull the product or service rather than pushing it on them. Second, eliminate any delays that may occur. Third, try to do more things in parallel rather than sequentially. Fourth, stop any unnecessary processing actions. Finally, eliminate excessive movement.

According to Alblooshi et al. (2021), Lean is centered on boosting the speed and

efficiency of processes by minimizing waste. Meanwhile, Six Sigma (SS) is dedicated to eliminating flaws and defects throughout the entire product lifecycle to enhance product and service quality. LSS combines both Lean and SS with the goal of improving business performance, enhancing process effectiveness and efficiency, and increasing customer satisfaction and profitability. LSS takes into account both process aspects, such as process capability and measurement, and human aspects, such as leadership, teamwork, and cultural change. By integrating the tools and techniques of both Lean and SS, LSS offers a balanced approach that allows organizations to optimize the benefits of each tool and adopt problem-solving techniques that suit their specific context. This approach facilitates the establishment of an infrastructure that supports process improvement throughout the organization.

Further, Arthur, (2016) noted that the seven understood speed bumps of Lean address waste, where any process that consumes cash, time, and workers but that does not generate value is considered non-value-added work. Toyota describes these as :

Overproduction is the most widespread type of waste that occurs when more products are made than necessary. For instance, taking blood samples from every patient "just in case" is a classic example of overproduction.

Excess inventory resulting from overproduction is considered waste. Similarly, if the Emergency Department (ED) processes patients faster than the nursing units can accommodate, patients are "boarded" in the ED. Patients in the ED waiting area are considered as excess inventory, while those in an ED exam room for lab results are considered work in process (WIP). It is important to note that WIP is a problem, not an opportunity.

Waiting is an unproductive and frustrating experience, whether it is your patients waiting for the following value-adding process to start or your employees waiting for their computers to boot up. It can also be caused by missing supplies or late attendees, creating further delays. By minimizing waiting times, you can enhance the efficiency of your processes and offer superior service to your customers.

Unnecessary movement of patients, such as transportation, can be minimized by breaking down silos into cells, reducing the distance patients and products travel between

processes.

Unnecessary movement of employees and redesigning supplies and tools' locations within hospital departments can reduce staff travel by 40-50%, allowing them to spend more time with patients.

Unnecessary or incorrect processing: In today's world, it is pertinent to consider whether it is worth the time and resources of individuals to watch over machines that can be taught to monitor themselves. Toyota coined the term "autonomation" to describe the degree of automation incorporating a human touch. We should question involvement in tasks that do not create any positive value.

Defects leading to repair, rework, or scrap: The implementation of Lean methodology can effectively eliminate the first six types of waste. At the same time, Six Sigma can provide valuable assistance in reducing the seventh. By strategically reorganizing critical areas like emergency department, operating room, radiology, and nursing stations into production cells with proper size of equipment and changeover times, one can potentially remove seven out of eight wastes of non-value added time.

Waste of talent and ideas: Waste is not restricted to physical objects alone. It also encompasses the loss of talent, commonly known as the eighth waste in Lean methodology. Consider a skilled surgeon waiting for an operating room to become available or a nurse with innovative ideas to enhance workflow within a nursing unit but unable to implement them. Such scenarios result in the waste of their talent. Hence, it's crucial to evaluate your hospital's processes and workspace design to ensure that your staff's abilities are being utilized to their fullest potential. Remember, optimizing talent can lead to exceptional outcomes.

In other research Fiorillo et al.(2021) summarized waste in healthcare (**as detailed in Table 1**):

Type of Waste	Application to Healthcare
Transportation	It takes account of those movements of materials and workers that do not add value to the merchandise: unnecessary

	movement of patients and staff.
Inventory	It leads to higher financing and storage costs, higher defect rates, and patients waiting (i.e., drugs with excessive or scarce supplies).
Motion	It consists of physical motions or walking by workers that distract them from actual processing work: staff searching for equipment, drugs, and paperwork.
Waiting	It is idle time that occurs when time is used ineffectively: excessive waiting for exams result, staff or medicines; waiting caused by schedule mistake.
Over-production	Producing more than the customer demands or too early before there is the need is not necessary. It increases the time of lead and storage, i.e., unnecessary diagnostic, acting per schedule.
Over-processing	It occurs when workers are unintentionally doing more processing work than the customer requires in terms of product quality or features: unnecessarily repeating tests, asking for patient's details several times.
Defects	It may include errors in paperwork, late transport, production according to incorrect specifications, wastes of raw materials or generation of scrap, repeating tests because of errors, readmission because of failed discharge.

Table 1: Type of wastes in Healthcare – Source (Fiorillo et al., 2021)

Bharsakade et al. (2021) have defined the seven criteria of lean thinking in healthcare processes as well as the sub-criteria for each of the wastes. With the help of Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchical Process (FAHP) approach, the seven major types of healthcare wastes and 21 various dimensions of healthcare wastes were prioritized. It can also be useful in determining how lean or otherwise the process of delivering healthcare is. The outcomes derived from the fuzzy AHP technique are as follows, depicted in **Table 2**, which presents the different aspects of HCW with relative priority.

Rank	Waste Dimensions	Weight	Waste Category
1	Waiting for diagnosis	0.2003	Waiting
2	Patient movement	0.1181	Transportation
3	Equipment unavailability	0.0989	Motion
4	Waiting for admission	0.0901	Waiting
5	Re-admission	0.0768	Defects
6	Movement for equipment	0.0511	Transportation
7	Test duplication	0.0487	Over-processing
8	Staff movement	0.0454	Motion
9	Waiting for discharge	0.0398	Waiting
10	Emergency medicine unavailability	0.0372	Inventory
11	Improper layout	0.0344	Transportation
12	Lab tests	0.0284	Overproduction
13	Equipment errors	0.0246	Defects
14	Process duplication	0.0224	Over-processing
15	Excessive material stock	0.0167	Inventory
16	Procedural errors	0.0165	Defects
17	Staff location	0.0151	Motion
18	Scheduled follow-up	0.0123	Overproduction
19	Unwanted treatment	0.0083	Overproduction

20	Patient information	0.0075	Over-processing
21	Excessive data storage	0.0074	Inventory

Table 2: Priority of sub-criteria for leanness in the healthcare delivery system – Source (Bharsakade et al., 2021)

Pyzdek (2021) summarized lean thinking into the following five principles: Value, flow, perfection, pull, and the value stream. In healthcare, value refers to the benefits that patients receive from services or products. Determining the value of healthcare can be complex due to the subjective nature of health outcomes. Value stream mapping helps us understand the importance of each step in a process from the customer's perspective. Medical errors are among the top causes of death in the USA, often caused by the system rather than individuals.

As stated by Arthur, (2016), it is an intrinsic truth that, in most successful hospitals with more than five years of their establishment, the general defect rate is about 1 percent. However, it is possible to make a rapid transition to these levels without the use of many sophisticated instruments. The firms that applied lean tools dramatically lowered defects to 3% or below in approximately six months or to 0.03% in nearly two years. When you reach this level, it may be possible to enhance your work process design through the use of lean six sigma tools. However, once you get there, you will find that you might have the discipline, desire, or rigor necessary for making those tools work. There are three essential tools for reducing defects: Control charts monitor CTQ requirement levels, Pareto charts deal with the root causes, and Fishbone diagrams study root causes.

Control Charts

One way to improve a process is by making the invisible visible. This can be done by using special graphs such as control charts. Control charts show you when something unusual happens to your process. In most hospitals, there are a few main control charts that are commonly used: the following control charts: XmR chart for cycle times and moving range, p chart for fraction defective, u chart for defects or frequency, or g chart in cases of “never events.” These charts can be used in various applications such as financial management, patient satisfaction, wait times in emergency departments or outpatient clinics, falls per 1,000 patient days, and more. By using control charts, you can easily monitor your process and take corrective

actions if necessary. An example of an XmR chart of bed wait times is illustrated in **(Figure 2)**. (Arthur, 2016)

Figure 2: XmR chart of bed wait times – Source (Arthur, 2016)

Pareto Analysis

Vilfredo Pareto was a polymath from Italy in the 19th century whose contributions spanned multiple fields, including engineering, sociology, economics, politics, and philosophy. The most famous is the Pareto principle or the 80/20 rule, which states that 80% of all problems are attributed to 20% of probable causes. Pareto analysis, highlighted in **(Figure 3)**, a Lean tool, utilizes this principle to identify the few critical sources responsible for the majority of issues, as well as hidden opportunities disguised as problems. This technique is particularly useful for breaking down large projects into more manageable sub-projects. Pareto analysis is essential for determining which project to pursue initially and which problems to address first. (Pyzdek, 2021)

Figure 3: Pareto chart of reported problems – Source (Pyzdek, 2021)

Root Cause Analysis

In Lean, problem-solving addresses the root causes of problems, not symptoms. Dr. Kaoru Ishikawa developed cause and effect diagrams, also referred to as fishbone diagrams, as a visual tool to showcase collective insights regarding the root causes of a given issue. These diagrams, as highlighted in **(Figure 4)** take on the shape of a fish's skeleton and are effective in illustrating potential causes contributing to a problem. Industry 4.0 has brought about a new wave of technological advancements that can revolutionize the way we conduct business. In more detail, the various tools of Industry 4.0 for simulation, predictive modeling, AI, process mining, data mining and big data analytics, IoT, and deep learning are more helpful in assisting with the various phases of a project. One of their most significant contributions is assisting in the root cause analysis process, which can help identify the underlying problems that lead to a particular issue. With these state-of-the-art tools at our disposal, we can improve our problem-solving capabilities and make informed decisions that can drive our businesses forward. (Bhat et al., 2023)

Figure 4: Structure of cause and effect diagram – Source (Pyzdek, 2021)

DMAIC & PDCA

The Six Sigma methodology uses the DMAIC acronym, representing five stages: defining the problem, measuring defects, analyzing root causes, implementing countermeasures, and controlling the process. The Theory of Constraints (TOC) states that operating at full capacity doesn't make sense if there's a bottleneck. TOC involves five steps: identify the weakest

link, optimize its performance, adjust the pace of other processes, invest in reducing the constraint, and repeat until the desired performance level is achieved. (Arthur, 2016)

According to Pyzdek (2021), the Kaizen approach is centered around the principle of continuous process improvement by involving everyone from top executives to floor workers. Instead of making drastic changes, Kaizen focuses on small, incremental improvements that can accumulate into significant results over time. This approach seeks to optimize existing processes for better outcomes rather than overhauling entire systems. The Kaizen approach implements the PDCA (plan-do-check-act) framework. Ideas for job improvement are actively solicited, changes are made to test ideas, and if positive results are obtained, permanent procedures are revised. Please refer to **(Figure 5)** for an illustration of the PDCA framework.

Figure 5: PDCA improvement cycle – Source (Pyzdek, 2021)

Value stream mapping

A value stream is defined as a collection of necessary, value-adding, or non-adding activities to transport a product through the mainstream channel from raw materials to a finished product in the hands of the customers. Value stream mapping is a technique for identifying the value stream of a manufacturing company by mapping the whole flow of material and information. A value stream aims to be tasked with defining and eradicating wastes at the earliest opportunity. In order to accomplish this, it is essential to consider the overall view of the processes rather than just the processes themselves and enhance the whole flow rather than the parts. Value stream mapping is a methodological approach that is used to define directions for

improving an organization. It establishes a standard approach for the whole process and helps to make better decisions to enhance the value stream. Overall, VSM is a good practice for incorporating lean practically. It is used to create a flowchart of the process starting from the first step to the last one, detect inefficiencies, and also make sure all organizational operations meet their efficiency targets and are not faulty in any way (Manzoor et al., 2022)

As pointed out by Pyzdek (2021), the process of creating a value stream map involves two crucial stages. Initially, we need to map the process's current state, followed by applying Lean principles to identify and eliminate any inefficiencies. By doing so, we can create a more efficient and refined process that delivers greater value to the customer while reducing waste. Overall, value stream mapping is a vital step towards achieving continuous improvement and enhancing the overall customer experience.

5S (sort, straighten, shine, standardize, and sustain):

The 5S methodology is one of the fundamentals of Lean management. It comprises five key steps: The program comprises of Sort, Set in order, Shine, Standardize, and Sustain. The details of each step are as follows:

- Sort: Distinguish between necessary and unnecessary items and eliminate the latter.
- Set in order: Arrange essential items in a way that facilitates easy access.
- Shine: Maintain a clean and orderly workspace.
- Standardize: Establish a system to ensure consistent organization in the workplace.
- Sustain: Foster a habit of sustaining a clean workspace. (Pyzdek, 2021)

JIT

According to Lawal and Elegunde (2020), Just-in-Time (JIT) is a manufacturing approach that responds to customer demand by pulling parts rather than pushing parts through manufacturing based on projected demand. JIT has proven to be a highly effective method for reducing inventory levels, improving cash flow, and minimizing space requirements. Research

indicates that JIT is crucial for ensuring efficient supply chain management. The JIT process incorporates principles of lean manufacturing, such as JIT inventory, JIT production, JIT human resources, JIT quality, and JIT supply relations.

Businesses often use "push" systems to make large volumes of identical items at low cost, hoping to sell them. This method relies on stable environments and predictable demand, which isn't always the case. "Pull" systems only produce items as needed, responding to changing demands. A well-organized emergency department is an example of a pull system. However, pull systems require consistent loading and flexible processes to function effectively. (Pyzdek, 2021)

2.3 Lean impact on supply chain efficiency

Operational efficiency is a crucial metric for evaluating a company's performance. It considers factors that include inventory turnover, cost control, and cycle time, among others. Many scholars have engaged in research that analyzes the effect of Logistics and Supply Chain Management practices and techniques on multiple operation performance metrics at the same time, as well as examining how Logistics and Supply Chain Management contextual factors can affect it (Moyano-Fuentes et al., 2020). The operational performance reflects the internal effectiveness of the company, referring to consistency, the production cycle time, and the inventory turnover. The three primary factors of operational performance are quality, cost, and time. Organizational work context cleanly translates to lean principles, which enhance the three dimensions of operational performance. In particular, Lean principles, including perfection, value, and VSM, influence the OpPerfCost. The pull principles generate positive improvements to cost reduction, while flow principles negatively impact performance (Thoumy et al., 2022).

Moyano-Fuentes et al. (2020) pointed out that applying lean supply chain management practices can help decrease variability and increase efficiency by reducing cycle time. Adopting a supplier integration strategy can also lead to lower costs and better results across the entire supply chain. By implementing Value Stream Mapping (VSM) techniques throughout the supply chain, it is possible to achieve cost and lead time reductions. Moreover, upstream supply chain management practices can help minimize operational and inventory costs. Implementing integrated logistics in supply chain management environments can make order cycles more

reliable, reduce inventory and operational costs, and provide other benefits as well.

Adopting Lean Supply Chain practices is critical for manufacturing companies in developing nations seeking to boost their competitiveness in fast-paced and competitive markets. Through successful implementation of SCM, Lean Supply Chain principles can be integrated, enabling companies to add value to their products by minimizing waste and inventory. This approach enables firms to sell products faster, freeing up storage space and reducing the cost of handling excess inventory. By operating from a properly sized warehouse, companies can concentrate on other aspects of their business, enhancing overall efficiency. (Istimaroh et al., 2022)

Pyzdek (2021) stressed that lean methodology aims to create an efficient process that consistently provides value to customers while minimizing waste. This involves getting rid of any type of waste that may occur. In an ideal situation, a healthcare facility would immediately initiate the necessary treatment to restore the patient's health, involving well-trained staff, timely supply delivery, flawless task performance, and clear instructions on discharge. Continuous flow is a process where a single unit of a product is produced and moved along the chain without delay, errors, or scrap. It has several benefits, such as reduced costs, instant quality problem signals, and no work-in-process inventory. Discontinuous flow leads to higher costs, delayed quality problem signals, and accumulation of work-in-process inventory.

A study conducted by Uddin et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of effective SCM in determining the success of a company. Proper management of the supply chain can yield substantial improvements in a business's operational and financial outcomes, resulting in increased productivity, reduced costs, and a sustained competitive edge. To fully leverage the benefits of supply chain management and enhance overall business performance, it is crucial to form strategic partnerships with suppliers and other stakeholders. Such partnerships can help in optimizing supply chain operations and achieving business objectives. Supply chain management unites supply and demand and positions each organization and supply chain's actions during supply chain processes, which leads to increased output, reduced cost, shorter time, higher revenue, and customer satisfaction. SCM manages the delivery of products and services to end consumers and manages the suppliers in order to unlock the value of the product or service to the

consumer.

Ramori et al. (2021) describes a case study conducted at a general hospital on implementing vendor-managed inventory (VMI) to address supply chain issues. Researchers used a structured intervention plan based on four pillars: processes, organizational structure, information systems (IS), and infrastructure. However, implementing VMI was not without challenges, particularly in adjusting IS. Varying perspectives on the implementation of VMI were revealed in the interviews conducted.

Another efficiency measurement pointed out by Pyzdek, (2021) is continuity of operations, which involves comprehension of customer need and required quantity, and items at the right time. This demand is referred to as takt time, which is determined by a special formula ($\text{Available Time Per Day} / \text{Customer Demand Per Day}$) to facilitate equalization along the value stream. For instance, we assume that a disability claims office is open from 9:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m., with a lunch break of 1:00 p.m. to 2:00 p.m. and two breaks of 10 minutes each. According to this scenario, the office has 400 minutes per day for work. If they get 50 claims on average per day, the takt time turns into 400 divided by 50, or 8 minutes per claim. Therefore, the office should strive to settle one claim in 8 minutes. Filing more claims than this would suggest that some positions are unnecessary, which would mean overstaffing. On the other hand, filing fewer claims than this would ensure that the customers would take so much time waiting for their payment on their claims, thus, wastage of time.

As stated by Basal and Sarkbay (2023), consumer behavior includes all actions of consumers during the process of purchasing, utilizing, returning, re-buying and sometimes rejecting both products and services. Consumer mood affects consumer behaviour, and those in good moods are more likely to exhibit a Variety of consumer Behaviour. Finally, in this evaluation stage, the consumers may develop new beliefs or inferences from the stimuli that have been classified. Brand equity, which defines a consumer's attitude and emotional response towards a brand, greatly impacts people's buying decisions and is primarily determined by the brand image. The overall objective of marketing communications for marketers is to change the perception and attitude of consumers towards a particular brand and build the right image of the brand in the minds of consumers so that they are persuaded to buy the product. It assists in the

enhancement of sales, attaining the maximum market share, and improving brand recognition among consumers. Brand image remains a critical factor in consumer decision-making, while brand qualities and attributes affect the frequency and quantity of brand consumed. Despite shifts in the consumers' daily lives and their ways of acquiring and filtering information, brand image has been found to be the key to customers' decisions.

Activities within projects need to have structures, processes, and ongoing assessment and enhancement plans for the steps taken and the results measured. Companies employ process quality improvement techniques to increase the quality of their processes in order to deliver value-added services to their clients. Lean management proves ineffective and unnecessary actions, leading to an overall improvement in the company's profitability. The healthcare industry should be cognizant of the five Lean performance measures, which address the human asset, quality, service, cost, and growth aspects of Lean (Kurdi et al., 2023).

2.4 Lean Philosophy Application in Healthcare Supply Chain Management

According to the Complementary Theory and Sustainable Lean Iceberg Model, Lean healthcare is a concept that can be measured using five first-order constructs: Strategy and Alignment, Leadership, Behavior and Engagement, Process Management, Tools, Technologies, and Techniques. The goal is to measure the association between Lean healthcare and the quality of healthcare services provided (San & Salleh, 2022)

For instance, when lean management was implemented in a US not-for-profit clinic, it improved the morale and job satisfaction of medical assistants, primary care physicians, and medical assistants. There was a work redesign/ workspace redesign, and Lean management-inspired changes to the process map, reporting, and working style were associated with increased employee involvement and decision-making, as well as upward communication and integration. However, over time, there was a significant imbalance between job resources and demands, leading to a decline in working conditions. Combining workstations of care team members helped staff spend less time locating each other and facilitated sharing patient information, resulting in enhanced communication and collaboration. (Mahmoud et al., 2021)

The use of Lean management has yielded many benefits when it comes to organizational practices, including improving the quality of products and services, reducing costs incurred, and

an overall increase in production rates. Lean management has been implemented at the operational, strategic, and policy levels in the context of healthcare organizations in different healthcare services and specializations, such as emergency departments, operating rooms, mental healthcare services, pharmacy services, information departments, and ambulatory care clinics. It has been proved in different analyses that using clinical decision support can reduce the time for those who arrive at the emergency room, reduce the rate of medical errors, and enhance the clinical pathways. (Mahmoud et al., 2021)

Previous research has revealed that to achieve sustainable Lean healthcare, it is necessary to integrate quality clinical practices with efficient process management. This integration leads to a continuous process flow that enhances patient-centered care without interruptions. Therefore, implementing process management is crucial in Lean practice to optimize process flow, reduce non-value-added elements, and ensure a steady delivery of value to patients.(San & Salleh, 2022)

Ramori et al. (2021) pointed out a cost model that was carried out to enhance the quality of the emergency department's services and the costs of using Lean Six Sigma. Some of the scopes used in the study include comparing today's process cost with the future process cost and developing the cost model of the emergency department. It also offered methods on how to reduce waste and increase quality as well as profit. The research employed activity-based cost analysis, which involves process mapping, cost model construction, and spreadsheets. Nevertheless, this research noted that the process changes in the emergency department were associated with a potential negative effect on the functioning of the department.

Additionally, Arthur (2016) highlighted several case studies in his book related to the lean application in healthcare. The Cincinnati Children's Hospital Medical Center (CCHMC) discovered that the flow of patients through the 25-bed Pediatric ICU was causing bottlenecks and gridlock.CCHMC found that patient demand can be random or non-random. To improve patient flow, the hospital made several changes in 2007, including limiting surgeries and scheduling postoperative ICU beds. These changes helped reduce diversions, boarding, and cancellations and increased the daily census from 17 to 21. The hospital was able to increase capacity without adding beds and expanded to a 35-bed ICU in 2009.

Borges et al. (2020) highlighted that implementing the policies for each supply chain

product by conducting a continuous inventory review management approach with three crucial parameters: cyclic stock, safety stock, and reorder point. The cyclic inventory calculation for supplier replenishment time was based on an average time, while products were categorized using the ABC classification according to their annual demand. The proposed real service levels for product types A, B, and C were tailored to their medical criticality. Achieving a 100% service level for delivery was a key focus, and reducing lead time was identified as a strategy for achieving overall cost savings. Lean principles, such as optimizing the requisition process, implementing visual management at each inventory location, and refining the reorder point, maximum and minimum stock control, and the pull system, can be effectively applied to enhance efficiency.

The implementation of lean tools in the healthcare context has shown positive impacts on various aspects, such as organizational, social, clinical, and cost. The effects include a decrease in the LOS and lead time, increased patient-centered services, staff, patient/family interactions, decreased infection rates, shorter treatment spans, increased revenues, and cost-effectiveness. These impacts are interlinked, emphasizing the efficacy of lean methodology in achieving superior outcomes that extend beyond mere modifications in work processes.(De Barros et al., 2021)

In 2008, the ICU department at Seattle Children's Hospital encountered inventory management difficulties. However, the hospital implemented the Lean system along with Kanban inventory management, which led to the creation of color-coded and fully stocked racks with two bins per item. When one container becomes depleted, it is sent to the central collection for replenishment while its barcode is scanned to produce new orders for error prevention. These enhancements have reduced patient costs by 3.7%, resulting in a total savings of \$23 million. The hospital has also demonstrated an efficient use of its current facilities, avoiding costly capital improvement projects despite the rising demand for patient care. (Arthur, 2016)

Kurdi et al. (2023) have highlighted the importance of lean knowledge practices in healthcare institutions. By implementing these practices and spreading them throughout the organization, healthcare institutions can achieve improved organizational performance. This can be achieved by effectively managing quality and resources to attain competitive performance.

The ability to manage quality and resources is crucial in achieving competitive performance, which in turn leads to better organizational performance. Therefore, healthcare institutions should prioritize the implementation of lean knowledge practices to achieve better performance and outcomes.

Arthur (2016) shared another case study that highlighted the successful reduction of monthly denied claims worth over \$1 million in just five days. The team used Pareto charts to narrow down the focus to a few key areas that required improvement. This helped to identify the GAP in the timely filing. By conducting a root-cause analysis session, they were able to identify ways to change the process that contributed to the denials and modify the contract process. The changes made helped to reduce delays, which in turn led to fewer timely filing denials. Additionally, the team worked with the insurer to ensure smoother operations.

According to Basal and Sarkbay (2023), healthcare providers who successfully implement lean management could lead to improved health and a guaranteed quality life for the masses. One factor contributing to the spread of mouth diseases is the tendency for people not to notice changes in their oral health and accept diseases as a normal occurrence. Additionally, many individuals find dental care unpleasant and, therefore, neglect their oral health. Another issue is the lack of public awareness regarding the importance of oral health for overall well-being, which may be due to limited access to oral health treatments and a lack of basic knowledge on the topic.

Basal and Sarkbay (2023) pointed out that the application method of lean management can enhance public health, especially oral health. Sadly, people do not pay much attention to the changes in their teeth health, and this sadly leads to dental diseases. This is the main reason why the people have no knowledge concerning the importance of oral health. According to the survey conducted by De Barros et al. (2021), several issues related to Lean Healthcare Philosophy and Lean Six Sigma, these issues have been addressed in the context of healthcare services. Such approaches have been applied to solve operational problems within intricate scenarios to make operational performance gains more possible. However, these tools cannot be easily implemented, considering that many companies experience difficulties in using Lean tools presupposes not only a clear understanding of Lean's philosophy but also a correct approach,

which is the methodology.

2.5 Potential Benefits Of Lean on Profitability

For the past twenty years, healthcare professionals have utilized various lean tools. While many organizations have effectively reduced expenses, decreased errors, and increased profitability, outcomes from implementing lean approaches in healthcare have been inconsistent. The efficacy of lean methods remains inconclusive as some organizations have achieved positive results while others have not, as evidenced by existing literature (Abdallah, 2020). From the perspective of Istimaroh et al. (2022) six main interrelated and non-trivial practices were found as the coherent constituent of LSCM. The best practices are customer relationship management, supplier relationship management, just-in-time manufacturing, waste control, cost control, and less inventory.

A quantitative study by Iswanto and Rosady (2020) evaluated Lean implementation that has successfully been adopted at a children's outpatient pharmacy in Jakarta Indonesia to determine the factors involved. At one month of implementation, the inventory cost came down from \$22,494 to \$15,128 monthly, with a drastic reduction of the medicine component of cost. The overall savings planned in three months were one hundred US dollars seventy seven thousand one hundred and ninety seven only while the cost of implementation was thirty three US dollars thousand seven hundred and thirty three only. According to the findings of the study, it is recommended that Lean should be applied in different units in a hospital while regarding the stock of medicines for any other eventualities in the future.

Having a proper financial performance measurement system is crucial for any business. It not only helps improve financial performance but also has a significant impact on supply chain performance. Therefore, it is widely acknowledged that the financial performance of a company is highly influenced by the performance of its supply chain (Iswanto & Rosady, 2020). Lima et al (2021) have identified that Lean Healthcare could be effective in increasing productivity while creating significant savings. It saves time, is gained from better timekeeping, organization, and planning, reduces costs, increases efficiency and quality, and is an effective means of eradicating errors and defective products and methods. Significantly enhanced standards of staff and patient satisfaction. An aggregated analysis has been made in order to guide the researchers and the

practitioners about the kind of improvements that have been documented and the corresponding results. These results include:

- a. Reduction of lead time, patient waiting time, hospitalization time, and waiting lists, resulting in time gains.
- b. Identification and reduction of waste, stocks, and costs, leading to a reduction of errors.
- c. Inter-group cooperation and information sharing, contented employees and suppliers, better work distribution for nurses, less overtime, and enhanced organizational culture.
- d. Bottleneck identification, improved patient and information flow, and capacity leveling, leading to efficiency and productivity gains.

The process of production scheduling involves managing the allocation of available resources, including equipment, labor, and facilities, to ensure necessary work is carried out efficiently and profitably. This is a tactical process that involves achieving a number of key objectives, for instance, high resource utilization, and low inventory. While long production runs and centralized manufacturing and distribution centers can generate economies of scale, short production runs and just-in-time delivery of raw materials are also necessary to minimize inventory costs. Achieving these objectives while maintaining high levels of production can be challenging, but it is crucial for achieving optimal performance and profitability. (Kozak et al., 2020)

For healthcare quality, we often think of clinical care and measures taken by organizations like the Joint Commission and National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators. However, there's more to it than that. Improving the financial or "transactions" side of healthcare can also help reduce costs and boost profits. A hospital faced 37,000 rejected insurance claims worth millions of dollars. Fixing these rejections and appeals was challenging. Clinical and operational aspects must work seamlessly to minimize costs, improve outcomes, and maximize patient satisfaction. (Arthur, 2016)

Rahiminezhad Galankashi and Mokhatab Rafiei (2022) explored the link between supply chain measures and the supply chain financial performance outcomes. Prior works have established that financial indices validate SCSs' effectiveness. These measures employ ratios concerning with the monetary cost and benefit systems of organising similar to physical clues. Thus, it is the financial goals that define whether the applied strategies, their outcomes, and the extent of their implementation correspond to supply chain profitability. Some of these goals consist of financial profitability, not compromising on liquidity and solvency, increasing the shareholder's wealth or value, and focusing on sales turnover. To achieve profitability, it is important to have an accurate financial performance measurement system.

According to Arthur (2016), it is clear that even a small percentage improvement in waste can lead to a large improvement in both productivity and profitability. Running a business can be challenging, but with the right dashboard metrics, you can identify areas for improvement without taking time away from your daily operations. Kurdi et al. (2023) define leanness more generally as the efficiency improvement in the context of the healthcare system cost and response time. To achieve this, healthcare systems need to focus on improving their resource utilization, providing high-quality care, enhancing the effectiveness of their diagnostic procedures, treating more patients quickly, and optimizing their facilities.

Experienced employees, medicines, devices, and equipment are central to quality healthcare but may become a concern due to shortages, putting patients at risk and leading to liability lawsuits. This was evidenced by the practice that oversupply led to wastage, theft, and obsolesce. The research reveals that healthcare is more exposed to inventory accumulation and product obsolescence than any other sector. Healthcare facilities keep inventory in different locations, including warehouses, pharmacies, operating theaters, and supply rooms. By the standardization of the software and data segmentation, costs and performance are optimized. Managing inventories is an important aspect of the overall nourishment of the supply chain in healthcare facilities (Essila, 2022)

According to Taheri et al. (2023) the current fast-paced and fiercely competitive business landscape, effectively managing inventory and financial flows has become a daunting task. Given the intertwined nature of inventory and financial flows, developing a comprehensive

strategy to tackle both aspects concurrently can greatly boost a company's overall productivity.

Therefore, great emphasis has been made on the management of supplies. However, it is not the only reason that can help improve the business situation for the better. Supply chain finance (SCF) solutions can play a vital role in enhancing a company's performance by minimizing financing costs and improving cash flow. When combined with robust supply chain management strategies, such as efficient inventory management and flexible production planning, SCF solutions can help to achieve a significant competitive advantage. Despite the increasing evidence of the benefits of SCF, there are still research gaps and inconsistencies that need to be addressed. (Uddin et al., 2023)

Competitive performance is achieved by producing high-quality results. Lean practices can help companies compete by improving flexibility, reducing costs, managing quality, and increasing customer satisfaction. (Kurdi et al., 2023)

According to recent studies, companies that adopt lean supply chain approaches have a beneficial effect on consumer purchasing habits. Additionally, convenience, efficiency, time management, and transportation are some of the critical criteria that have significantly influenced consumer purchasing patterns in recent times. (Basal & Sarkbay, 2023)

Narayanan et al. 2022 have described that Lean systems in Denver Health Medical Center were able to achieve a net saving of \$2.8M while improving no negative impacts on staff and patient care. Introducing technical trays introduced cost-saving climaxes of directly to 20% in an academic hospital. Further, Value stream mapping enhanced the hospital billing revenues by 5 percent. Some of the benefits realized from Lean implementation were enhancing of the productivity, reduction of the cost, and the showed better financial performance. At a mental health center, applying C.I and V.S mapping enhanced the services by 27% and the reduction of no-show rates by 12%, implying an increase in the revenue. Another paper by Rosa et al. (2021) has revealed that Virginia Mason Medical Center has indeed adopted lean manufacturing technique from the manufacturing industry into healthcare. The hospital has adopted a management model they call Virginia Mason Production System based on Toyota Production System but is still under enhancement. This has led to enhancement of service delivery, decreased time and operational cost.

Optimizing supply chain management can be highly advantageous for businesses. By doing so, they can minimize costs, reduce waste, lower purchasing expenses, and optimize inventory levels. Such improvements often lead to increased revenues, as product quality, turnaround times, and adaptability all benefit from a streamlined supply chain. Moreover, optimizing working capital can also enhance financial performance by reducing inventory and streamlining payment and receipt processes. Finally, identifying, evaluating, and mitigating supply chain risks can further benefit businesses. The bottom line is that an effective supply chain management strategy can significantly impact a company's overall success. (Uddin et al., 2023).

2.6 Lean Impact On Patient Outcomes

Heijndermans et al. (2020) has postulated that this Lean approach instrumental in enhancing patient-centeredness through progressive improvement of work. This means that each member of the production system will focus on reducing the waste and increasing the value added work in efforts to improve both patient and staff satisfaction, decrease waste, clutter, and confusion, eliminate defects, reduce expense, and increase profit. Several processes analyzed under this method include the Lean method, where every step involved in any production process is analyzed to establish if at all it has any value to the patient. Despite the fact that most of the studies published in the contemporary context of Lean in healthcare concern the first three principles, the long-term impact of Lean principles, including on-demand patient production (pull system) and ongoing improvement pursuing perfection, remains an area of research.

Muharam and Firman (2022) affirms that the management concept of "lean" is widely recognized and implemented. The study demonstrated the effective application of lean methodologies in healthcare, with remarkable outcomes such as a 42% decrease in paperwork, improved collaboration among multidisciplinary teams, and a 33% reduction in length of stay. In addition, other authors have pointed out that lean tools and practices allow for a decrease in the duration of patient waiting time, the optimization of patient logistics, increasing in service speed, and patients outcomes, and a decrease in mortality. The implementation of the Lean Six Sigma approach can effectively minimize the risks associated with healthcare-associated infections.

Iswanto (2021) observed that a pharmacy department in the US was able to cut down up

to one-third in drug selection errors, up to half in prescription mistakes, and up to two-thirds of mistakes arising from similarity through implementing LSS methodology. They also effectively applied LSS to resolve waiting time problems, and in this manner, waiting time could be cut by as much as 50%. For example, in Jordanian hospitals, LSS has proven effective in cutting down the cycle time of drug dispensation by up to 45 percent. Clinically, by optimizing medication choices and dosing while minimizing mistake occurrence and time spent waiting or processing, healthcare facilities stand to boost their bottom line overall.

Healthcare providers in both developed and developing countries use Lean Six Sigma to enhance their performance and productivity while staying within budgetary limits. This methodology lowers costs, improves service quality, increases patient safety, and delivers services on time. Integrated Lean Six Sigma strategy in healthcare fosters a culture of continuous improvement, reduces medication errors, and improves patient care quality, ensuring customer satisfaction. Lean Six Sigma is an excellent operational excellence strategy that lowers healthcare operational costs, decreases non-value-added activity, and enhances healthcare experiences. (Bhat et al., 2023)

Narayanan et al. (2022) explained that the benefits of improving the flow of patients through surgical clinics and operating rooms in a hospital by deploying lean practices can be seen in two main ways. Firstly, it can lead to a higher quality of care, which means patients are served better and experience lower wait times. Secondly, it can increase the number of patients that can be served in a given time frame, thereby improving the hospital's throughput. This can potentially lead to higher revenues as a result of the improved quality of care, which attracts more patients to the hospital. A lean project that improved service capacity in a clinic by 27% and reduced no-show rates by 12% resulted in higher revenues.

A study done by Muharam and Firman (2022) was in line with other studies done at a teaching hospital outpatient clinic in Brazil. Based on the findings supported by quantitative and qualitative analysis of lean management theories, it is possible to provide shorter patient waiting times. Likewise, a study done on tertiary hospitals in Abu Dhabi found that effective waiting times were reduced to 4-6 minutes from 40-60 minutes after the introduction of lean management principles. In another study conducted at a reproductive clinic in China, the use of

the PDCA cycle showed that patient waiting time was significantly reduced during outpatient procedures by 128.83 minutes. Furthermore, the study revealed that patients' satisfaction rose by 24.07 after adopting the aforementioned strategies.

According to a recent study, Suman and Prajapati (2021) highlighted that the duration of a hospital's delivery room stays significantly impacts the quality of service. Employing the Lean Six Sigma methodology, the researchers found that a lack of delivery rooms is the primary reason for prolonged stays. They proposed several protocols and procedures that successfully reduced the average stay from 11.9 hours to only 3.4 hours. The women's medical center clinic implemented the Six Sigma Define-Measure-Analyze-Improve-Control (DMAIC) philosophy, resulting in a significant decrease in wait time from 38 to 8 days and a 73% increase in revenue.

Fiorillo et al. (2021) established waste and inefficiency value stream map within the preoperative process. This was a result of affecting the LOS before surgery, which is the overall key performance indicator. Using the Ishikawa diagram, the researchers were able to determine the major causes of such inefficiencies, thereby being able to ponder over the possible solutions. The main corrective action was the creation of a pre-hospitalization service. The comparison of statistical data also confirmed the impact of the solutions adopted and revealed that the average preoperative LOS was reduced by 22.40%, from 4.90 days before the changes to 3.80 days after the implementation of the solutions.

2.7 Lean Philosophy Implementation Challenges

The disruptions by COVID-19 have several lessons that healthcare hospitals could learn from. It can also adapt the nested warehouse logistics process recipes, such as the utilization of automation technology to improve supply chain inventory processes. As seen above, process automation, which helps companies such as Amazon, is not easy to implement in the healthcare sector because of the logistics involved. Due to some of the constraints, such as financial constraints, legal requirements, and organizational culture, there is decision-making difficulty in this healthcare sector. The healthcare sector has intentions of minimizing inventory expenses, but the intended goals are rarely realized. (Essila, 2022)

Medical supply chain management research typically focuses on minimizing costs and optimizing profits through various inventory management techniques. However, in a pandemic

context, lean inventory systems can't keep up with demand. The need for global access to essential medical supplies supersedes costs and profits. Businesses, humanitarian logistics organizations, and governments must address inventory issues to ensure a functional healthcare supply chain network. (Friday et al., 2021)

Alblooshi et al. (2021) research has identified that successful LSS (Lean Six Sigma) projects require three key factors: structure that are management commitment, training, and organizational support. On the other hand, ignorance, change management issues, people's resistance to change, and poor support from managers are some challenges facing LSS projects. The impacts of LSS applications can be categorized into four areas: On the industrial level, on the organizational level, individual and general effects of LSS. Prior work suggests that organizational consequences are reported to be amongst the top-five identified effects and that LSS can generate individual effects as well.

Lima et al. (2021) research has identified several factors that can impede the successful implementation of Lean practices. These include:

- a. Insufficient training and a lack of trust in Lean practices among teams can create long-term obstacles to sustainable Lean implementations.
- b. Limited focus on the overall process vision and a prevalence of isolated initiatives (known as "local vision").
- c. Inadequate involvement of stakeholders and operational teams leads to demotivation and poor team performance.
- d. Challenges with data collection and storage problems creating accurate information.
- e. One of the major limitations, which has been highlighted in several studies, is the lack of communication between Lean professionals and other professionals, particularly care professionals such as nursing and clinical staff, as well as traditional managers.
- f. Excessive bureaucracy in the hospital field, with regulations, protocols, and

legislation often being used to block or compromise Lean applications.

According to Rosa et al. (2021), in many cases, lean methodologies are introduced and implemented partially, and their application is manifested only by individual processes within the value chain or in specific technical processes. At the present time, very seldom can one observe hospitals' handling of lean as a systemic integration. That is why the absence of successful implementation of lean methodologies has also emerged as a popular focus of discussion.

The practical application of Lean Six Sigma in the healthcare system depends on the country being referred to. Evidence of its effectiveness in hospitals is lacking. To realize its potential, a comprehensive approach with effective deployment and sustainment strategies is essential. Restructuring the organization, upskilling the workforce, and managing resistance to change are necessary. Communication should be clear that improved processes and project failures will not result in job cuts. An ecosystem for innovation, risk-taking, and critical thinking toward value propositions must be established. (Bhat et al., 2023)

Suman and Prajapati (2021) discussed the state of affairs in Saudi Arabia about Lean Six Sigma in hospitals. Also, the utilization was still in its infancy in those organizations. They also discussed other works that compared the Lean Six Sigma and implementation of quality performance in Malaysian hospitals. The analysis indicated that the staff from the public hospitals and private hospitals had significant differences concerning Lean and Six Sigma projects.

Adopting a lean philosophy within emerging economy organizations is difficult because of Resource constraints and the culture's effects on employees. However, the need to use lean techniques is rising due to global competition. Barriers to LP implementation are organizational culture, lack of commitment from top management, middle management behavior and employee attitudes, inadequate knowledge about the implementation process, restrictions on budget, and past experiences with failed lean projects. (Manzoor et al., 2022)

Lean principles can be challenging to apply in healthcare due to the unique characteristics of healthcare services. Healthcare services are intangible, heterogeneous, perishable, and

simultaneous, which makes them different from manufacturing. Despite the perception that Lean was designed only for manufacturing, research shows that it can be applied to healthcare. Lean thinking is a process-focused philosophy that emphasizes process improvement over products. It can be applied to healthcare because healthcare services involve individuals and items that interact in various processes. Lean has become a primary focus in healthcare management literature, and Lean Healthcare has received positive feedback for improving healthcare service quality. (San & Salleh, 2022)

Recent studies have revealed the positive impact of Lean Six Sigma methodology on process efficiency, finances, and organizational behavior. To effectively implement this approach, it is crucial to prioritize management commitment, organizational culture, and training. Nonetheless, hurdles can arise during the implementation process due to limited awareness of Lean Six Sigma tools and benefits, as well as resistance to change and a lack of effective change management. (Alblooshi et al., 2021)

Concerns about the planning and control of medical inventory have always been considered significant challenges in medicine logistics and supply chains. CPFR practices enhance the management of inventory, financial and operational firm performance. The COVID-19 pandemic caused an unprecedented surge in demand, limiting the responsiveness of the globally interconnected medical inventory system. Adding capacity from global supply chains takes longer, making it more challenging to meet sudden demand surges, especially when there is panic buying and limited collaboration among healthcare supply chain actors. (Friday et al., 2021)

While most studies on Lean practices tend to focus on just one aspect and assume that each practice can independently improve quality, effective Lean implementation requires a more comprehensive and holistic approach. All practices must work together in a more extensive management system to achieve optimal results. Implementing Lean practices in isolation often leads to minimal contribution. To address this issue, complementarity theory can be used to view Lean practices as second-order formative constructs where they mutually support each other and have complementary effects. However, further research is necessary to confirm the complementary measurement of Lean practices, particularly in healthcare. A study is needed to

develop and validate comprehensive Lean healthcare practices that can significantly enhance healthcare service quality.(San & Salleh, 2022)

Rosa et al. (2021) explained that healthcare in the past decade has experienced more pressures such as demand pressure comprising of the shifts in patterns of prevalence of diseases and the pressure for quality and safety. Similarly, the adoption of new technologies has also challenged the cost factor since adopting new technologies and changing the strategies that are aligned with them are expensive exercises. These challenges are further compounded by available health system resources, which are dwindling, together with the policy of patient access to care irrespective of ability to pay that is embraced by most countries. To fulfill patient requirements, it is necessary to employ several resources that are rare, such as a specified number of beds, technological instruments, staff with identified clinical competencies, medical instruments, and reportage.

The implementation of lean methodology in public healthcare systems can enhance process quality and avoid wastage. The length of stay is a crucial metric to evaluate healthcare process performance, measuring the duration of a patient's hospitalization from admission to discharge. Although clinical diagnosis can affect the length of stay, poor healthcare process management can also prolong it. Inadequate standardization of healthcare processes is frequently responsible for prolonging the length of stay in such cases. (Fiorillo et al., 2021)

2.8 Lean Philosophy Implementation Limitations

Lima et al. (2021) discovered that there's a significant disparity in the amount of work dedicated to integrating streams compared to work organization, visual management, and diagnostic and problem-solving tools. The observed increase in results aligns with the fundamental principles and foundations of lean philosophy. However, the improvement results are presented in fragmented activities and lack empirical evidence supporting their consistent long-term sustainability.

It is important to note that the introduction phase of implementing the Lean method is a critical moment. This phase helps to reduce distrust and resistance to change within the organization. It demonstrates the benefits of Lean and evaluates the organization's ability to adopt continuous improvement. Numerous case studies have reported successful implementation

of Lean in healthcare settings by utilizing Lean tools and techniques. (Rosa et al., 2021)

The first issue that arises when discussing Lean within the healthcare context is that Lean is still a relatively young approach in the sphere. As a result, it is hard to get evidence from one organization that can persuade the rest of the top management about the advantages of the concept. As is the case with many critical theories, it is essential to bear in mind that breaches of assumptions that underpin lean may be critical; matters like the definition of the customer and the limitations inherent in designs around capacity in seeking to shape demand or utilize the times freed up when embracing Lean could be some of the significant areas of concern in the context of healthcare organizations. However, certain factors regarding the Lean transformation in the healthcare field are more or less the same for all countries. For instance, there are disparities in the business practices of private and public healthcare organizations, resulting in dissimilarities in implementing Lean. (Reponen, Rundall, Shortell, Blodgett, Juarez, et al., 2021)

According to San and Salleh (2022), the implementation of Lean methodology requires five crucial elements. These include strategy and alignment, leadership, behavior and engagement, process management, and technology tools and techniques. Many organizations tend to focus only on the visible indicators of Lean practice, such as process management and technology tools, as these elements are "above the waterline". However, in order to sustain Lean and gain a competitive advantage in the long run, the 'below the waterline' factors, such as strategy and alignment, leadership, culture, and employee commitment, also need to be adopted.

Ensuring psychological safety is a critical factor in fostering a comfortable work environment, particularly when implementing lean practices geared toward waste reduction. When employees feel psychologically secure, they are more inclined to take part in process improvement initiatives that could potentially eliminate certain tasks or functions, including those performed by themselves or their colleagues. By instilling a sense of security, employees are more likely to take an active role in lean initiatives, leading to the application of innovative problem-solving methods and increased motivation to utilize lean tools. In healthcare settings, employee empowerment cannot be fully realized without first ensuring psychological safety.(Narayanan et al., 2022)

Studies suggest that approximately 70% of Lean organizations ultimately fail due to a

lack of employee engagement and a reluctance to change. This resistance is understandable, as embracing Lean principles often requires adjustments to both work processes and employee behavior, leading to feelings of insecurity and uncertainty. In order to ensure a successful Lean transformation, it is essential to address these concerns and invest in employee training and incentives to promote engagement and empowerment. Ultimately, a successful Lean healthcare implementation hinges on the presence of respected, accountable employees who understand their role, share the organization's Lean goals, and exhibit Lean behavior and engagement. (San & Salleh, 2022)

2.9 Tailored Approaches and Strategies

According to a study conducted by Reponen et al. (2021), implementing Lean practices in the public sector may require a customized approach. This is due to the conflicting political, regulatory, and commissioning priorities that public healthcare institutions often face. Additionally, the presence of heavy bureaucracy, strict policies, and regulations can hinder flexibility and make the implementation of Lean practices more challenging. Nevertheless, despite these obstacles, Lean management has been successfully implemented in public hospital settings worldwide.

The use of cross-functional teams has been observed to be effective in enhancing processes in the healthcare sector. It is a common occurrence that in healthcare facilities, different organizational power dynamics exist between physicians and other employees. The use of cross-functional teams will assist in properly implementing lean methods. This is even more relevant because different readers are interested in different things and need different information. To simplify the text and make it comprehensible, we divided it into logical sections and placed the most significant information into sections with low numbers. It doesn't use any complex structures; the focus is on simple and concise, always avoiding extra words in a sentence. We have confined ourselves to business parlance and prefer the active voice for words. We have also applied the active voice to enhance comprehension, where the subject performs the function of the verb (Narayanan et al., 2022).

Accurately measuring a project's deliverables is a vital aspect of the lean philosophy. To ensure success, it's critical to prioritize Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which may include

minimizing expenses, enhancing productivity, reducing waste and variability in processes, and improving delivery time. By focusing on these KPIs, organizations can select the right projects and improve their circular economy. It's not enough for lean philosophy projects to only consider Critical to Quality (CTQ); Critical to Business (CTB) or Critical to Costs (CTC) should also be taken into account. Involving the financial department in lean philosophy projects can be beneficial in choosing the right projects and monitoring progress. It's also essential to establish an effective and dependable feedback system to track the project's status. Healthcare organizations face unique challenges when identifying relevant process parameters and gathering reliable data. Therefore, it's important for hospitals to identify the appropriate project KPIs from the customer, business, and social perspectives. (Bhat et al., 2023)

Narayanan et al. (2022) emphasize that healthcare frontline staff face complex challenges not seen in manufacturing settings. Hospitals are dynamic service settings with rapidly changing and uncertain environments. Although lean systems can help, implications in service settings like hospitals may differ from manufacturing. Lean implementation can improve both cost and revenue performance, leading to better financial outcomes.

Thus, the promotion of Lean culture in an organization is a critical goal and one of the key ways to progress in this area is training employees in the use of tools applied to the Lean concepts. Behavior is what drives change, so it is more effective when people actually do something rather than think or feel. Therefore, it is recommended that management raises awareness of Lean within their organizations in order to enhance the understanding of each principle. Nonetheless, Lean's implementation into a company's ethos can be a tough endeavor. If the goal is to have more positive impact, then it is recommended that management work on the most important behaviours and the mindsets will adjust accordingly. In time, these changes in behavior and habits will pay a better dividend. In light of the current uncertainty and ambiguity, especially in the context of the global pandemic, the results of this study in relation to the effects of Lean production on operational performance are still valid. (Thoumy et al., 2022)

2.10 Future Directions and Recommendations

As noted by Khorasani et al. (2020), while existing literature frequently highlights the benefits of incorporating lean practices into supply chain management (SCM), these advantages

are not always accompanied by quantifiable metrics, and the associated costs are often overlooked. Furthermore, future research should explore the impact of implementing multiple lean applications in each area of lean implementation, as many studies tend to focus on a single or limited number of applications, neglecting to account for their interrelationships.

As suggested by several impressive and extensive studies conducted on the topic of assessing the supply chain performance, it has been noted that a large number of them do not pay adequate attention to the aspect of financial indexes. In other words, despite the growing use of non-financial indicators in recent years, supply chain managers rely a great deal on financial facets while evaluating performance. This goes to show the importance of the financial aspects in assessing the total performance and productivity of the supply chain. By incorporating financial measures, it will be easier for the organizations in question to make the right decisions as well as gain a competitive edge over the other players within their industries using the information given. (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022)

Manzoor et al. (2022) in their research study pointed out a research gap by raising the need for lean philosophy in the current phenomenal business environment. Corporate players must replicate cost control and optimize organizational performance at the tactical level to develop the right quality products for global markets. The importance of lean thinking has been rising to eliminate waste and boost effectiveness. The implication of the results is that lean philosophy enhances the performance of the firm and financial performance.

While analyzing the literature, Narayanan et al. (2022) identified that the research gap includes the fact that the relationship between lean implementation in hospitals and the impacts on financial performance has been discussed insufficiently. Published works have attempted to examine the application of lean in the hospital and its effects. A study also employed the use of ANOVA to establish that if a hospital uses lean, it is likely to record improved EBITDA performance. Nevertheless, these studies do not embrace lean implementation in terms of the social context and with regard to financial repercussions.

Further, routine cross-comparative studies should be conducted to evaluate the impact of culture on Lean in healthcare settings. This type of study has not been covered in studies in the recent past due to a lack of comparative studies based on multi-site datasets, and there are no

applied internationally comparable outcome domains to frame such studies. IT is crucial to recognize the status of Lean implementation outside of the organizational boundaries in order to support the goals of performance improvement. (Reponen, Rundall, Shortell, Blodgett, Juarez, et al., 2021)

The researcher also noted that there was a dearth of research on the use of LSS (Lean Six Sigma) in the ME (Middle East), East Asia, North Africa, and Europe. In addition, where there were very few Malaysian studies, these were cross-sectional in nature, sector-specific, and, at times, limited to local regions and used single-source case studies. The role of size as a control variable, the level of process investigational complexity, and the viewpoints on the processes by which LSS can be applied simultaneously were unspecified. This, in a way, hinders the generalization of results since the findings only apply to the sample taken and not the whole population. Thus, further investigations have to examine organizations that are more numerous, cross-sectional, and drawn from a wider geographic area than the samples used in the studies reviewed in this paper. These could help in better understanding of requirements and constraints, risks, and benefits of LSS applications and generalisable knowledge about other contexts.(Alblooshi et al., 2021)

There is a widespread use of lean management in healthcare organizations for performance improvement, but cross-national benchmarking is not often used. Variations in the model of healthcare systems present certain constraints for benchmarking. There is an absence of empirical research on lean implementation in the international setting. More studies are required in the area of cross-national benchmarking of lean in hospitals to identify the pros and cons of benchmarking. (Reponen, Rundall, Shortell, Blodgett, Jokela, et al., 2021)

Maturity level pertains to the understanding and proficiency gained through process improvement endeavors, encompassing familiarity with methodologies and tools, self-assurance, reliability, and dissemination within the organization. An organization with a low maturity level is susceptible to failure in both its processes and overall functionality. Progress may be sluggish and occasionally exasperating until the organization attains a just maturity level. Nonetheless, as the level of maturity increases, integrating lean practices becomes a routine undertaking rather than a sequence of projects that occur at isolated intervals.(Rosa et al., 2021)

LSS consists of Lean and Six Sigma, which can help enhance process performance, but it does not guarantee effectiveness due to factors like training and education, supplier involvement, management commitment, costs, habit changes, and resource reduction. LSS at the hospital level is relatively challenging when compared to the unit level, and some significant issues have arisen in raising efficiency overall because the clinical staff is highly specialized and divided into professional domains. Hence, effective LSS projects are mainly at the unit level. (Iswanto, 2021)

Despite the growing interest among countries in enhancing their performance, international adoption of benchmarking remains limited. However, exploring this field can yield valuable insights. By conducting cross-comparative research, we can gain a deeper understanding of the utilization of Lean methodologies in healthcare and identify any cultural factors that may impact its adoption and implementation. (Marsilio et al., 2022)

According to a recent study by Suman and Prajapati (2021), the implementation of Lean or Six Sigma methodologies in healthcare organizations in India is still relatively low. However, the study highlights that hospitals adopting these methodologies perform significantly better than those not. Additionally, hospitals are evaluated based on their performance with and without implementing quality initiatives. This suggests that there is a strong case for healthcare organizations in India to consider adopting Lean or Six Sigma methodologies for better performance.

Lean production is a methodology that emphasizes the efficient use of resources, as opposed to the traditional mass production approach. The objective is to reduce human labor, manufacturing space, tool investment, and engineering hours by 50% while launching a new product in half the time. Moreover, it entails maintaining a significantly lower inventory on-site, resulting in fewer defects and enabling a broader range of products to be manufactured. (Sonali et al., 2022)

To achieve timely results and accomplish Lean Six Sigma project objectives, it's not enough for top management to simply make the team aware of the goals and expected outcomes. On the other hand, it is the responsibility of the top management to give the push by getting rid of barriers, availing adequate financial and human resources, ensuring proper project tracking, and recognizing effective teams. (Bhat et al., 2023)

The establishment of psychological safety is imperative in the implementation of lean practices within hospital settings. It is crucial to foster an environment where employees feel secure in expressing their opinions and ideas, free from the threat of critique or persecution from their colleagues. This safety is centered around the notion that taking risks and conducting experiments will not result in negative consequences. Within healthcare, psychological safety is deemed an essential component for the effective implementation of lean practices and sharing of knowledge. It is defined at the individual, team, and organizational levels and serves to promote learning behavior among employees. As such, psychological safety is vital to the social context of lean implementation within hospitals. (Narayanan et al., 2022)

A recent study by Kurdi et al. (2023) has identified a significant relationship between process quality improvement, lean activities and strategic competitiveness. The problem is that, given the significant amount of resources and efforts being devoted to healthcare quality improvement, there are relatively few studies that would illustrate the effects of organization's quality-related operations and activities. Therefore, it can be concluded that this field requires additional research.

In their research, Basal and Sarkbay (2023) emphasized the significance of streamlined and easily accessible supply chains for dental hospitals. Patients seek top-notch, reasonably priced, and informative services, along with efficient post-treatment care. Dental hospitals can fulfill these expectations by taking into account patients' individual preferences, including age, gender, race, social class, and marital status. By accommodating such preferences, patients can enjoy a variety of options as they embark on their dental care journey.

2.11 Conclusion

Lean philosophy is a popular manufacturing method where wasteful practices are eliminated. This enhances processing time and ensures consistency in supply and demand. By implementing lean tools, the companies can work towards the goal of making considerable financial improvements by establishing the proper flow of goods that eliminate the muda or waste. Here there was evidence that lean could be classified into strategic and tactical levels of daily use. Strategic lean is applicable in creating value where as tactical lean applies to certain details in a certain field. Tactical lean encompasses those practices that organizations employ in

their business activities using the lean methodology with different tools and techniques.(Manzoor et al., 2022)

"Lean healthcare" aims to eliminate waste in all areas of the healthcare business to reduce inventory, service cycle times, and costs while maintaining high-quality patient care. Waste refers to any work activity that does not add value. Lean is a methodology that focuses on eliminating waste and increasing added value of products, goods, and services to provide value to customers.(Andriyani et al., 2021)

(Lima et al., 2021) illustrate that hospital dynamics are based on more or less complex interconnections between people and activity flows across different tiers of structural specialization and identification. The nursing and the administrative personnel are contractually bound to the hospital and governed by its structure chart, but the medical group is fairly clinical process independent. Overall, there is need for hospitals to adopt increased professional management style like those environments of the business organizations. Thus, despite their large number of structures that is associated with their capacity, hospitals are generally not easy to change. Hospitals, like any other organization, need to have a culture of operating improvement and operations management on going.

Collaboration is key in planning, forecasting, replenishing, and managing risks in Healthcare Supply Chains (HCSCs). Collaborative efforts help ensure better access to essential medical supplies, particularly during pandemics. To this end, we have devised two models, each consisting of three propositions, that explain how a collaborative approach can help maintain optimal medical stocks and build the resilience of HCSCs (Friday et al., 2021).

Several scholars such as (Ramori et al., 2021) have hinted that hospitals and care facilities should consider adopting lean business models to enhance patient care, management of resources, and employee satisfaction. From literature review, it was found out that process improvement cost models, lean thinking models, managerial process improvement and care models were useful in solving challenges within the healthcare industry. Further, sustaining competitive advantage was essential in responding to the value proposition stakes established by customers and competitors. As a result, it is likely that hospitals and care facilities should take into account the lean business models for attaining these goals in their organizational strategy.

(Argiyantari et al., 2020) highlighted the strategic management approach in healthcare service organizations, emphasizing the lean principle. Since the lean supply chain has been applied in healthcare for a relatively shorter period, the existing research supports its usage in this sector. Notably, healthcare enterprises have shifted their focus from push systems to informational system-based distribution systems. For instance, the industry employs vendor-managed inventory (VMI) and the Kanban system to optimize its operations.

Based on the research framework discussed by (Marsilio et al., 2022), it is recommended to examine the relationship between Lean adoption/implementation and performance consequences. Despite this approach being slightly more system-wide, as seen with public hospitals in the US, their perceived performance outcomes indicate that the Lean implementation that they undertook produced comparatively lower outcomes than those witnessed in the case of Italian hospitals. Thus, it is critical to carry out an analysis of Lean through the means of impartial and relevant performance indicators. The availability of research on Lean and other like transformational performance related programs can help policymakers and practitioners alike to make optimal choices to enhance PS hospitals' performance in all countries.

(Muharam & Firman, 2022) identified in their studies the various benefits, which lean management brings to a specific health service system that integrated fertility clinic falls because it is easy and inexpensive to apply. If lean management is implemented in clinical procedures, it can also result in efficient operations. (Reponen, Rundall, Shortell, Blodgett, Juarez, et al., 2021) Stressed that, through Lean, frontline staff are enabled to make decisions and drive further waste reductions. There is relatively little benchmarking research carried out in Lean healthcare, and the majority of it is restricted to intra-organizational research, along with regional and national investigations. Benchmarking measures that are most frequently employed are service provision-related measures of process outcomes, and there appear to be no equal sets of measures. Decision-makers should involve leaders in evidence-based practices while acknowledging the lack of knowledge about contextual factors. It will help to perform benchmarks and disseminate leanness in Lean healthcare organizations by using a conceptual framework. Regarding the gaps for future research, the author suggested international benchmarking, identification of key factors that define Lean initiatives, patient benchmarking, and system benchmarking.

One of the studies by (Lima et al., 2021) aimed to identify Lean Healthcare practices in three Brazilian hospitals. The research revealed that these hospitals utilized similar tools and frameworks, such as PDCA, DMAIC, value stream mapping, and kaizen. The implementation of Lean Healthcare was driven by strategic planning. The most commonly used methods included process vision, team decision-making, RIEs, Value Stream Mapping (VSM), and Standard Work (SW). Among these, Visual Management (VM), Ishikawa Diagrams, and DMAIC stood out as prominent problem-solving tools.

In their study, (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022) discussed financial performance measures for supply chain analysis. Some researchers proposed using a Balanced Scorecard - Analytic Hierarchy Process (BSC-AHP) model to evaluate supply chain performance. The study suggested several financial considerations for assessing supply chain performance, including customer query time, net profit/productivity, rate of return on investment, variance to budget, buyer-supplier partnership level, delivery performance, supplier cost-effective measures, delivery reliability, cost per operation hour, information carrying cost, and supplier rejection rate. In the services supply chain, where the BSC has been used to measure performance, financial measures such as ROI, gross revenue, profit before tax, and cost reduction were utilized.

As explained by Taheri et al. (2023), effective inventory management is crucial for a company to achieve positive outcomes. By keeping track of the cost of capital and obsolete materials, a company can prevent unnecessary expenses and ensure that its resources are used efficiently. Additionally, by converting excess inventory into profitable products, a company can generate cash flow and increase its overall profitability.

"Lean" is a cost-effective tool that helps increase profits by reducing costs, waste, and improving quality and productivity. Supply chain processes can be streamlined to adapt to changing business trends and consumer demands. Lean philosophy plays a key role in optimizing business processes.(Manzoor et al., 2022)

In their research, (Narayanan et al., 2022) stated that there are limited research studies that have established an empirical link between lean implementation and financial performance. Some research studies that have been conducted have actually observed that lean practices do not

impact costs. Various studies have been conducted to examine the outcomes of applying lean techniques in different manufacturing settings by using various performance measures. However, these results cannot be generalized to healthcare or other service operations because there are fundamental differences between manufacturing and service domains.

The application of Lean Six Sigma (LSS) approaches can greatly improve the efficiency of hospitals by reducing the length of stay (LOS) for patients in both the ambulatory and hospital-based settings. LOS is the number of days it takes for a patient to be admitted and then discharged from the hospital normally in a day's unit. Notably, LSS has proven to be effective in reducing costs for patients requiring prolonged hospitalization (LOS >4 days). However, further research is required to fully explore this issue.(Iswanto, 2021)

The implementation of the lean principle has brought about significant benefits for the pharmaceutical industry. By placing emphasis on reducing wasteful practices such as inventory, high investments that yield low returns can be avoided. Introducing integrated planning, production, distribution, and purchasing can greatly improve inventory management within the pharmaceutical supply chain. This is a promising sign that the pharmaceutical supply chain is making positive strides toward enhancing its working capital performance and boosting company profitability.(Argiyantari et al., 2020)

A study made by (Argiyantari et al., 2020) showed that by the deployment of Lean Six Sigma, there has been a reduction of inventory purchases in the pharmaceutical unit despite the pandemic as well as the new normal era. The reduction was 27 % prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, 29% during the COVID-19 pandemic, and 37% in the COVID-19 new normal in contrast to the pre-LSS period. This contributor to improving hospital efficiency and operation is also evidenced by the reduction of the hospital's deficit by 26% before the pandemic and 10% during the pandemic in comparison to the time before the LSS was put into practice. However, the new normal saw the deficit rise by 29%, informing that the impact of LSS on the hospital profits was reduced.

According to a recent publication by Taheri et al. (2023) Coca-Cola made significant improvements to their cash flow management, resulting in a remarkable 40% increase (nearly \$2900 M) in cash flow in 2021 compared to the previous year. In today's competitive business

landscape, managers must consider uncertainty when making critical decisions. By understanding the intricate relationship between suppliers, manufacturers, and distributors, managers can chart a clear path for their company's mission and foster brand loyalty over time. However, it's essential not to overlook inventory levels despite the positive impact of cash flow management. Research has shown that poor cash flow planning can cause significant harm to a company or even an entire country, as evidenced by Greece's downturn in 2015 due to a staggering \$400 billion national debt (equivalent to 170% of their GDP). Similarly, the COVID-19 pandemic's economic emergency led to a decline in capacity utilization and forced some producers to adjust their inventory costs.

Patient satisfaction and experience are essential in healthcare. Satisfaction is a competitive advantage, while experience goes beyond it. Patient satisfaction depends on organizational culture, responsiveness, information, expectations, and perceptions. Patient experience is affected by uninformed expectations and perceptions about the healthcare system. Implementing lean principles in healthcare can improve patient satisfaction, but it requires the support of key stakeholders. (Nino et al., 2021)

According to Morell-Santandreu et al. (2021), Implementing the Lean philosophy in healthcare can make necessary changes and improvements. Reorganizing agendas based on care needs reduces workload, creates new patient care circuits, and better allocates resources. Using Lean methodologies leads to long-term sustainability in economic, social, and environmental aspects. This methodology can be applied to other primary care centers to reduce barriers and limitations.

(Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022) highlight the SCOR model's role in assessing supply chain performance. The model's financial performance metrics are categorized into strategic, tactical, and operational perspectives for comprehensive evaluation. Although financial performance is crucial to upper management, the SCOR model has also been linked to other performance aspects. These financial measures can be applied at various decision-making levels, making them useful for managers in different situations. The supply chain has four interconnected cycles: procurement, manufacturing, replenishment, and customer order cycles. Please refer to **Table 3**.

No	Supply Chain Cycle	Financial Measures	Strategic	Tactical	Operational
1	Procurement cycle	- Cost - Inventory turnover - Cash-to-cash cycle	✓	✓ ✓	
2	Manufacturing cycle	- Cost - Inventory turnover - Revenue growth - Cash-to-cash cycle	✓	✓ ✓	✓
3	Replenishment cycle	- Cost - ROA - Sales - Cash-to-cash cycle	✓	✓ ✓ ✓	
4	Customer order cycle	-Cost - Market share - Inventory turnover - Cash-to-cash cycle			✓ ✓ ✓ ✓

Table 3: Cycle view of the developed framework – Source (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022)

The management of supplier and customer relationships with the aim of delivering exceptional customer value while reducing costs across the entire supply chain is what is commonly referred to as supply chain management. In today's competitive business environment, supply chains are pitted against each other, and their prosperity hinges on how well they serve their customers. To remain viable, most supply chains must deliver the appropriate product in the correct quantity and quality, at the ideal price, and at the optimal time to the precise customer. To achieve this, some companies have adopted lean supply chain (LSC) principles to revolutionize their supply chains.(Cvetić et al., 2021)

The first two lean principles are to define value and map the value stream. By understanding the reasons behind gaps in the process, such as non-value-adding practices and

facility arrangements, we can implement the following two principles: creating flow and establishing pull. Lastly, the fifth principle emphasizes the need for continuous improvement, as there is always room for it. (Nino et al., 2021)

By implementing lean tools, methods, and techniques in the supply chain, significant benefits can be achieved with minimal investment. These benefits include reduced waste and costs, improved quality, faster delivery times, and, ultimately, increased profitability for the supply chain. (Cvetić et al., 2021)

The United Kingdom and the United States were the first countries to introduce lean thinking in healthcare in 2001 and 2002, respectively. In the last 20 years, developing countries have also adopted lean implementation in healthcare. This implementation has resulted in both tangible and intangible benefits, including the reduction of procedural errors, waiting times, and costs, as well as increased patient satisfaction, improved healthcare delivery quality, and increased patient motivation. Lean methodology helps to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of healthcare delivery processes. Healthcare organizations can achieve lean implementation through continuous improvement, which can improve their quality. Lean implementation in healthcare can also enhance flow efficiency, reduce costs, and improve quality. (Bharsakade et al., 2021)

According to Ahmad et al. (2021) Lean, it is a method that reduces waste and waiting time in healthcare. Long waiting times can cause mental health issues. By improving flow, distance, time and increasing the number of patients, lean improves service quality in public healthcare. It aims to eliminate non-value-added activities and create value for end customers.

Lack of standardization was an issue in healthcare process even while pre-COVID, hospitals were inconsistent. This variability could increase costs since the poor quality products or services will lead to clients' disappointment. However, when the same was applied in the hospital's pharmaceutical installation, the organization noticed a steady drop in the procurement of pharmaceuticals. This decline was mainly due to the 5S and other supporting activities that cut across in an effort to eliminate many supplies in order to support movement and easy identification of drugs on the shelves. These activities also decreased wait time from 57 minutes to 27 minutes. This means LSS also made an impact, contributing to lower purchase and supply

costs at LSS despite the pandemic and the new normal.(Iswanto, 2021)

Ensuring optimal inventory levels in hospitals is critical to prevent wastage caused by overstocking or shortage of materials. Effective healthcare inventory management is key to maintaining system quality and measuring performance. It is especially important to keep emergency medicines in proper supply. Improper inventory control can result in other forms of wastage, such as excessive storage of patient information. Obtaining timely and relevant information is crucial to ensure efficient healthcare operations.(Bharsakade et al., 2021)

CHAPTER III: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework guiding this study explores the influence of Lean Philosophy on the profitability of healthcare supply chains, particularly through the mediating effect of inventory waste reduction. Lean Philosophy, which originated from the Toyota Production System, focuses on maximizing value by systematically eliminating waste within processes. This research posits that the implementation of Lean practices in healthcare supply chain management can significantly enhance operational efficiency, reduce unnecessary costs, and improve profitability while also maintaining or even elevating the quality of patient care.

This framework places Lean Philosophy within the specific context of healthcare, recognizing the sector's distinct challenges, such as unpredictable patient needs, critical time constraints, and complex regulatory requirements. It contends that traditional supply chain practices often fall short in addressing these dynamic conditions, making Lean an appealing alternative. By prioritizing continuous improvement, process standardization, and waste elimination, Lean tools like Just-In-Time (JIT) inventory management and Value Stream Mapping (VSM) are anticipated to facilitate the optimization of resource allocation and operational practices.

Furthermore, this theoretical interpretation integrates aspects of organizational behavior theory, examining how the adoption of Lean Philosophy can not only enhance operational outcomes but also initiate cultural transformations within healthcare institutions. Such cultural shifts can promote teamwork and proactive problem-solving, which in turn further support continuous improvement and profitability.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework serves as a visual representation of the proposed relationships among Lean implementation, the reduction of inventory waste, and increased profitability within healthcare supply chains. This model outlines a detailed pathway that explains how the adoption of Lean practices can lead to significant improvements in financial performance. By focusing on enhancing process efficiency, Lean methodologies aim to streamline operations, reduce unnecessary delays, and eliminate waste associated with excessive inventory. As a result,

organizations can achieve not only cost savings but also improved service delivery, ultimately leading to higher profitability in the competitive healthcare landscape.

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework

The framework illustrates that Lean Philosophy provides two significant advantages: a direct enhancement of profitability and an indirect influence through the effective reduction of inventory waste. This dual effect underscores the critical importance of strategically implementing Lean practices within an organization. By systematically minimizing waste, companies can achieve not only lower operational costs but also foster more streamlined workflows, thereby enabling smoother processes and ensuring that resources are allocated in a timely manner. This holistic approach to waste reduction creates a more efficient operational environment, ultimately driving overall business success.

3.3 Key Constructs

Lean Philosophy: The study explores the impact of Lean practices on healthcare operations, particularly focusing on waste reduction, process optimization, and continuous improvement.

Inventory Optimization: As a mediator in the relationship between Lean practices and profitability, inventory optimization focuses on reducing excess inventory and ensuring timely supply availability, thus improving cash flow and reducing costs.

Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability: The dependent variable in this study is measured by the financial performance of healthcare organizations, particularly in terms of cost reductions, improved service levels, and overall financial health.

The framework posits that implementing Lean Philosophy leads to inventory optimization, which directly impacts the profitability of healthcare supply chains.

3.4 Definition of Terms

Lean Philosophy: Lean is an approach that aims to streamline processes by minimizing waste and enhancing value. Originating from the Toyota Production System, Lean is rooted in continuous improvement and optimizing resources to maximize value for the end-user (Arthur, 2016). Its application in healthcare has shown significant potential in reducing operational inefficiencies and improving patient care quality (Mahmoud et al., 2021).

Supply Chain Management (SCM): This term refers to the coordination of materials, information, and resources from suppliers to consumers (Uddin et al., 2023). In healthcare, SCM ensures that medical supplies, pharmaceuticals, and other essentials are delivered efficiently, impacting patient outcomes and operational costs (Borges et al., 2020). Effective SCM incorporates Lean principles to streamline processes and minimize waste (Kurdi et al., 2023).

Inventory Waste Reduction: Inventory waste involves holding excess stock that does not contribute to value creation, leading to higher costs and potential obsolescence (Fiorillo et al., 2021). The Lean approach targets waste reduction by employing strategies like Just-In-Time (JIT) inventory, ensuring stock levels meet demand without surplus (Arthur, 2016).

Profitability: Profitability in the context of healthcare SCM is defined as the financial performance resulting from efficient resource management and operational improvements. Lean implementation positively influences profitability by reducing waste and optimizing workflows (Istimaroh et al., 2022). Studies have shown that reduced lead times and inventory management contribute to better financial outcomes (Lima et al., 2021).

Value Stream Mapping (VSM): A crucial tool in Lean methodology, VSM helps visualize all steps in a process, identifying those that add value and those that do not (Pyzdek, 2021). By mapping out processes, healthcare organizations can pinpoint inefficiencies and areas

for improvement (Manzoor et al., 2022). VSM supports continuous improvement efforts and enhances process flow (Pyzdek, 2021).

Continuous Improvement (Kaizen): Kaizen is a Lean concept emphasizing small, incremental changes that collectively lead to significant improvements (Arthur, 2016). In healthcare, it encourages staff to contribute ideas for refining processes, fostering a culture of ongoing improvement (Mahmoud et al., 2021). Successful Kaizen initiatives have been associated with increased operational efficiency and enhanced patient satisfaction (San & Salleh, 2022).

Muda: Originating from the Japanese term for unnecessary spending, Muda represents any activity that fails to add value. In healthcare, Muda can manifest as redundant diagnostic tests, overstocked inventory, or inefficient administrative workflows, which inflate costs and hinder service delivery (Fiorillo et al., 2021). Addressing Muda is central to Lean efforts, aiming to eliminate non-value-adding processes and foster cost-effective care (Arthur, 2016).

Kanban: A visual system that controls the movement of materials and information within a process. In healthcare, Kanban aids in managing inventory levels to ensure supplies are adequately stocked and readily available, minimizing the risk of overstocking while avoiding shortages (Borges et al., 2020). Implementing Kanban supports efficient supply chain practices and improves resource allocation (Arthur, 2016).

Just-In-Time (JIT): A strategy where supplies are ordered and received only as needed, thereby reducing inventory costs. In healthcare, JIT ensures that essential supplies are on hand when required, minimizing storage expenses and mitigating stock obsolescence (Arthur, 2016; Uddin et al., 2023).

Takt Time: This concept defines the rate at which a product or service must be delivered to meet customer demand. In the context of healthcare, takt time synchronizes patient care activities with resource availability, promoting timely and efficient service provision (Arthur, 2016; Pyzdek, 2021).

Lean Six Sigma: A combined methodology that incorporates Lean's waste reduction techniques and Six Sigma's focus on reducing variance and defects. In healthcare, Lean Six

Sigma is leveraged to streamline operations, improve patient experiences, and lower operational costs (Narayanan et al., 2022). This integrated approach aligns continuous improvement with quality management for impactful results (Bhat et al., 2023).

Cycle Time: The total duration required for a process to be completed, from initiation to final delivery, including waiting and interconnection periods. Reducing cycle time in healthcare can expedite patient treatment, cut down waiting periods, and improve overall service quality (Mahmoud et al., 2021).

Bottleneck Analysis: This process identifies operational points that slow down workflow and create inefficiencies. In healthcare, bottleneck analysis helps optimize patient flow, reduce treatment delays, and enhance service delivery efficiency (San & Salleh, 2022).

Continuous Flow: A Lean principle that designs work processes to facilitate the uninterrupted movement of products or information. In healthcare, implementing continuous flow ensures that patient care is delivered consistently without unnecessary delays, improving service effectiveness (Arthur, 2016).

PDCA Cycle (Plan-Do-Check-Act): The PDCA cycle signifies a systematic approach to continuous improvement, emphasizing iterative problem-solving and process refinement. In healthcare, the PDCA cycle aids in enhancing care quality, reducing waste, and boosting patient outcomes (Pyzdek, 2021).

Lean Impact on Patient Outcomes: The application of Lean practices in healthcare has profound effects, such as significantly reducing waiting times, increasing treatment accuracy, and elevating patient satisfaction (Muharam & Firman, 2022). These principles foster a patient-centered approach that enhances the quality and timeliness of care (Narayanan et al., 2022).

Supply Chain Finance (SCF): These financial tools and practices are employed to enhance the financial management of the supply chain. In healthcare, SCF improves cash flow and reduces the costs associated with inventory and supply chain operations (Essila, 2022; Uddin et al., 2023).

Operational Efficiency: The capability of a healthcare organization to deliver high-

quality services cost-effectively. Operational efficiency is a primary outcome of Lean SCM, which supports cost control and process optimization (Arthur, 2016; Kurdi et al., 2023).

Strategic Alignment: Ensuring that Lean initiatives align with the healthcare organization's broader goals is vital for long-term sustainability and profitability. Effective strategic alignment underscores Lean practices as a sustainable investment in healthcare's future (Lima et al., 2021).

3.5 Detailed Explanation Using Key Constructs

The theoretical framework elaborates on the transformative potential of Lean Philosophy when implemented effectively within healthcare supply chain management (SCM). A key example of this is Just-In-Time (JIT) inventory management, which synchronizes the supply of medical resources with the actual needs of patient care. By doing so, it minimizes the amount of excess stock held, thereby significantly lowering storage costs and reducing the risk of waste due to expired or unnecessary inventory. This strategic alignment not only enhances operational efficiency but also underscores a crucial insight: healthcare institutions can achieve greater profitability through a balanced approach that emphasizes not only revenue growth but also rigorous cost management and waste reduction strategies. This comprehensive focus enables healthcare providers to deliver better patient care while maintaining financial sustainability.

Figure 7 Conceptual Framework Linked to Theoretical Framework

3.6 Integration of Research Questions and Survey Results

Interpretation of Research Questions:

RQ1: How can supply chain profitability be increased by applying Lean Philosophy?

The theoretical framework posits that adopting Lean practices effectively optimizes operational processes and minimizes expenses, which in turn enhances overall profitability. This viewpoint is substantiated by survey findings that demonstrate a clear and substantial positive influence of Lean practices on financial performance among respondents. Furthermore, the data indicates that strong leadership commitment to Lean initiatives, along with a relentless focus on continuous improvement, plays a pivotal role in driving profitability. By prioritizing these elements, organizations can create a culture that not only embraces efficiency but also fosters sustained financial success.

RQ2: How can Lean methods be effectively deployed in healthcare supply chains?

Successfully implementing Lean methods in healthcare is a complex process that necessitates careful strategic planning, extensive training, and robust organizational support. The findings from the survey reveal that, although a significant number of healthcare organizations have embarked on the journey of adopting Lean, they often face considerable obstacles. These challenges include initial resistance from staff and a lack of adequate training, which together serve to limit the degree of successful implementation. Respondents highlighted the critical importance of strong leadership support and well-designed training programs in fostering an environment conducive to Lean methodologies. This insight resonates with the theoretical framework that underscores the significance of cultivating a positive organizational culture and committing to continuous improvement. By prioritizing these elements, healthcare organizations can enhance their ability to fully realize the benefits of Lean practices.

RQ3: How does inventory optimization, influenced by Lean Philosophy, contribute to supply chain profitability?

The framework emphasizes the critical role of inventory optimization as a mediating factor influencing the connection between Lean implementation and profitability. Survey results

revealed that hospital respondents utilizing Just-In-Time (JIT) and various Lean inventory strategies experienced a significant decrease in inventory holding costs and waste levels. This reduction not only streamlined their operations but also had a direct and positive impact on their overall profitability. These findings support the theoretical model's assertion that effective Lean practices lead to enhanced inventory optimization, which is a fundamental outcome contributing to financial success in the healthcare sector.

CHAPTER IV: METHODS AND PROCEDURES

4.1 Research Design

A quantitative research design was adopted to examine the impact of Lean Philosophy on healthcare supply chain profitability. The quantitative approach was selected to systematically measure the relationships between Lean practices and profitability metrics across a sample of healthcare organizations. This design is aligned with the study's objective to provide statistically valid insights into how Lean Philosophy influences operational efficiency and financial outcomes in healthcare supply chains.

4.2 Data Gathering Procedure

Structured online surveys on Microsoft Forms were distributed to a targeted group of healthcare supply chain professionals in Saudi Arabia through their professional email using a convenient sampling method to collect data. The survey instrument was meticulously designed to capture relevant data on Lean Philosophy implementation, inventory management practices, and perceived impacts on supply chain profitability. The survey consisted of closed-ended questions, utilizing Likert scales to quantify participants' responses. The survey was administered online, allowing broad and efficient reach among the intended respondents. Before the distribution of the survey, a pilot test was conducted to refine the questionnaire and ensure the clarity and relevance of the questions. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, assured of their confidentiality, and provided with an option to withdraw at any time without any consequences.

4.3 Data Analysis Guide

The survey data collected from the respondents were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were used to tabulate and summarize data, while inferential statistics were used to test the Correlation between Lean practices and their connectivity with profitability measures. Furthermore, the research adopted a T-test analysis to test the study hypothesis.

The choice of these statistical methods was driven by their ability to effectively address the study's research question, providing a clear understanding of the quantitative impact of Lean

practices on financial performance within the healthcare sector.

Research questions and variables were explored in four dimensions of lean application consisting of Staff Commitment To Lean, Leadership Commitment To Lean, Continuous Improvement Model, and Financial Impacts of Lean Applications tied to research questions and variables as illustrated in the summary below table :

Dimensions	Survey Question	Variable	Research Questions
Staff Commitment to Lean	1-Is your hospital presently engaged in lean philosophy performance improvement approaches?	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Staff Commitment to Lean	2-The unit's staff are committed to and have a positive attitude toward lean philosophy.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Staff Commitment to Lean	3-The hospital has implemented a daily management system that uses the lean philosophy to ensure timely and correct work across all departments, helping to achieve the organizational goals.	Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability	Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?
Staff Commitment to Lean	4-The staff is committed to implementing a lean philosophy and developing ways to enhance its application.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Staff Commitment to Lean	5-The staff is encountering difficulties in implementing their lean philosophy ideas.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?

Leadership Commitment to Lean	1-The hospital leaders established benchmarks for efficiency and patient satisfaction to measure progress in their lean philosophy initiatives.	Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability	Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?
Leadership Commitment to Lean	2-Lean philosophy has a sponsor/champion and team members who demonstrate visible, active, public commitment and support of lean philosophy.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Leadership Commitment to Lean	3-Hospital managers have been trained to use scientific problem-solving methods, such as Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.	Inventory Optimization	Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?
Leadership Commitment to Lean	4-The manager in charge of the unit has a favorable attitude towards the principles of lean philosophy.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Continuous Improvement Mode	1-Improvement work is part of the regular work, and everyone feels that improvement work is important to the quality of healthcare provision.	Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability	Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?

Continuous Improvement Mode	2-Implementing a lean philosophy leads to organizational success through waste elimination, reduced expenditure, shorter stays, higher patient satisfaction, fewer sensitivities.	Inventory Optimization	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Continuous Improvement Mode	3-Every hospital staff member is highly skilled in identifying what patients find valuable, which is evaluated continuously.	Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability	Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?
Continuous Improvement Mode	4-There is a well-established process for conducting value stream mappings in the hospital. These mappings are constantly updated and used to improve patient care quality.	Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability	Q1 How to increase supply chain profitability by applying lean philosophy?
Continuous Improvement Mode	5-The hospital staff is highly skilled at creating and adhering to routines. In case of any errors or issues, the routine is used to identify the root cause of the problem.	Lean Philosophy	Q2 How to deploy lean methods in healthcare supply chain?
Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	1-The finance department provides revenue and expenditure projections to managers. This helps establish a reliable financial performance measurement system, minimizing costs, reducing waste, lowering expenses, increasing revenues, and optimizing inventory.	Inventory Optimization	Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?

Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	2-Organizations have effectively reduced expenses, decreased errors, and increased profitability, which are outcomes of implementing lean philosophy in healthcare.	Inventory Optimization	Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?
Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	3-Implementing the lean philosophy enables frontline staff to eliminate waste, achieving optimal inventory levels in hospitals that can prevent wastage due to overstocking.	Inventory Optimization	Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?
Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	4-Inventory optimization was achieved by implementing a lean philosophy and a quality improvement methodology.	Inventory Optimization	Q3 How to increase organization profitability by implementing an inventory optimization strategy?

Table 4: Survey Questions Mapping with Lean Application Dimension, Research variables & questions.

4.4 Scope and Limitation

4.4.1 Scope:

This study focuses on the application of Lean Philosophy within the healthcare supply chain, specifically targeting hospitals in Saudi Arabia. The primary scope includes analyzing how Lean practices influence the profitability of healthcare organizations by mediating inventory waste reduction. The research examines the theoretical integration of Lean principles, particularly in inventory management, and their impact on financial outcomes. This study also aims to outline a conceptual framework that links Lean Philosophy with improved healthcare supply chain profitability.

The study is designed to:

1. Review the deployment of Lean Philosophy in the healthcare supply chain.
2. Identify the sources of profitability in the healthcare supply chain.
3. Develop and test a conceptual framework that explores the relationship between Lean Philosophy and healthcare supply chain profitability.

4.4.2 Limitations:

- **Geographical Limitation:** The research is limited to hospitals within Saudi Arabia, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings to other regions or types of healthcare institutions.
- **Data Collection:** The study employs an online survey to gather data through convenient sampling, which may limit the depth of insights due to the potential for non-responsiveness and bias in participants' self-reported information. Moreover, the small sample size resulting from constraints related to time and resources restricts the study's findings. Additionally, the lack of multivariable analysis, such as regression analysis, further limits the scope of the research.

-

- **Focus on Inventory Management:** While the study emphasizes inventory waste reduction as a key mediator, other factors influencing healthcare profitability, such as workforce management or patient care processes, are not deeply explored.
- **Cross-Sectional Nature:** The study employs a cross-sectional design, capturing data at a single point in time. This may limit the ability to observe the long-term impacts of Lean implementation on profitability.
- **Lean Implementation Stages:** The study does not differentiate between organizations at various stages of Lean implementation, which may influence the outcomes related to profitability and efficiency improvements.

Despite these limitations, the study significantly contributes to the understanding of Lean Philosophy's role in enhancing the financial performance of healthcare supply chains.

4.5 Significance of the Study

This study holds significant value for multiple stakeholders within the healthcare sector:

1. **Healthcare Management:** By identifying the direct impact of Lean Philosophy on supply chain profitability, this research provides actionable insights for healthcare managers aiming to enhance operational efficiency and financial performance. The findings offer a roadmap for implementing Lean practices that can lead to substantial cost savings and improved service delivery.
2. **Policy Makers:** For policymakers in the healthcare sector, this study underscores the importance of adopting Lean practices as a strategic approach to managing healthcare supply chains. The evidence provided can support policy decisions aimed at fostering more efficient and sustainable healthcare systems.
3. **Academic Contributions:** The study fills a notable gap in the existing literature on Lean Philosophy's application in healthcare, particularly in the context of supply chain management. It contributes to the academic discourse by providing empirical evidence on how Lean practices can mediate inventory waste reduction to enhance profitability.

- 4. Future Research:** This research lays the groundwork for future studies that could explore other aspects of Lean implementation in healthcare, such as its impact on patient care or its application in different healthcare settings. It also highlights the need for longitudinal studies to assess the long-term benefits of Lean practices.
- 5. Practical Implications:** The insights from this study can help healthcare organizations refine their supply chain strategies, ensuring that resources are utilized more efficiently, inventory waste is minimized, and profitability is maximized. By demonstrating the financial benefits of Lean practices, the study encourages broader adoption of these principles across the healthcare industry.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter outlines the methodology used to quantitatively assess the impact of Lean Philosophy on financial performance in healthcare supply chains. It begins with a description of the survey used for data collection, emphasizing the reliability of responses through carefully designed questions. The chapter details the systematic process for gathering data from key informants in the health sector, including selection criteria and strategies to improve response rates. It then discusses the statistical techniques applied for data analysis, highlighting the software used and the rationale behind the chosen methods for evaluating Lean Philosophy's effects on profitability. The chapter also specifies the geographic scope and components of the healthcare supply chain studied, while acknowledging limitations.

CHAPTER V: DATA PRESENTATION

5.1 Descriptive Statistics

The conducted survey aims to explore the potential benefits of applying lean principles to healthcare supply chains, particularly considering recent global disruptions. Recognized by experts across various fields, the healthcare supply chain is crucial in balancing cost management with quality improvement. The healthcare industry's unique implementation of lean practices, which focus on eliminating waste and non-value-adding activities, is the subject of this investigation.

The survey is specifically designed for the administrative staff of hospitals in Saudi Arabia, aiming to understand the challenges and successes in implementing lean philosophy within their healthcare systems. The collected information was used to analyze the impact of lean practices on the profitability of the healthcare supply chain, building upon previous research while also exploring new factors of lean impact on profitability. It builds upon previous studies by (Kaltenbrunner et al., 2017) and (Shortell et al., 2021) incorporating customizations by the author to further examine the impact of lean practices on profitability.

The methodology of the "Impact of Lean Philosophy on Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability" survey involves a series of structured questions designed to assess the current engagement of hospitals with lean philosophy performance improvement approaches. The survey includes questions on staff commitment to lean philosophy, the implementation of daily management systems using lean philosophy, and the establishment of benchmarks for efficiency and patient satisfaction by hospital leaders. It also explores the support and commitment of hospital leaders to lean philosophy, including the presence of a sponsor/champion for lean initiatives and the training of managers in scientific problem-solving methods like Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.

Data from 39 respondents across 21 hospitals in Saudi Arabia revealed perceptions of lean management practices. Notably, 79% of these respondents have over ten years of experience.

Pie Chart - Responders Age*Figure 9: Respondent Gender*

Figure 10 Responders years of experience

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Staff Commitment To	39	100.0%	0	0.0%	39	100.0%
Lean Philosophy						
Leadership	39	100.0%	0	0.0%	39	100.0%
Commitment To						
Lean						
Continuous	39	100.0%	0	0.0%	39	100.0%
Improvement Model						
Financial Impacts of	39	100.0%	0	0.0%	39	100.0%
Lean Applications						

Table 5: Case Processing Summary

Descriptive statistics results were generated using IBM SPSS 26. The descriptive statistics for each variable are provided below in the table. Mean, standard deviation, minimum

value of the sample, maximum value of the sample, and 95% confidence interval are computed and presented. The variables are measured on the Likert 5-point scale of agreement, where '1' represents strongly disagree and '5' represents strongly agree.

The results indicate that the respondents generally have strong impact towards lean management practices, with the highest mean score for the continuous improvement model (4.18) and the lowest mean score for the staff commitment to lean philosophy (3.77).

The standard deviations for all variables are relatively low, indicating that there is not much variation in the responses. The minimum and maximum values show that none of the variables have extreme outliers. The 95% confidence intervals for the mean show that the true population mean for each variable is likely to be within the reported range.

Descriptives

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Staff Commitment To	Mean	3.77	.125	
Lean Philosophy	95% Confidence	Lower Bound	3.52	
	Interval for Mean	Upper Bound	4.02	
	5% Trimmed Mean		3.79	
	Median		3.80	
	Variance		.605	
	Std. Deviation		.778	
	Minimum		2	
	Maximum		5	
	Range		3	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.370	.378
	Kurtosis		-.318	.741
Leadership	Mean	4.01	.131	
Commitment To Lean	95% Confidence	Lower Bound	3.74	
	Interval for Mean	Upper Bound	4.27	

	5% Trimmed Mean		4.03	
	Median		4.00	
	Variance		.669	
	Std. Deviation		.818	
	Minimum		3	
	Maximum		5	
	Range		3	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.337	.378
	Kurtosis		-1.010	.741
Continuous	Mean		4.18	.102
Improvement Model	95% Confidence	Lower Bound	3.98	
	Interval for Mean	Upper Bound	4.39	
	5% Trimmed Mean		4.22	
	Median		4.20	
	Variance		.403	
	Std. Deviation		.635	
	Minimum		2	
	Maximum		5	
	Range		3	
	Interquartile Range		1	
	Skewness		-.748	.378
	Kurtosis		.424	.741
Financial Impacts of	Mean		4.13	.101
Lean Applications	95% Confidence	Lower Bound	3.92	
	Interval for Mean	Upper Bound	4.33	
	5% Trimmed Mean		4.14	
	Median		4.00	
	Variance		.398	

Std. Deviation	.631	
Minimum	3	
Maximum	5	
Range	2	
Interquartile Range	1	
Skewness	-.099	.378
Kurtosis	-.961	.741

Table 6: Descriptives

Normality Tests

The normality tests for each variable are presented in the table below. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests are used to test the null hypothesis that the data follows a normal distribution. The significance level is set at 0.05.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	p-value	Statistic	df	p-value
Staff Commitment to Lean Philosophy	.106	39	.200*	.964	39	.247
Leadership Commitment to Lean	.126	39	.121*	.916	39	.057
Continuous Improvement Model	.129	39	.099*	.934	39	.069
Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	.122	39	.151*	.931	39	.086

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Table 7: Tests of Normality

The normality tests for each variable are presented in the table below. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests are used to test the null hypothesis that the data follows a normal distribution. The significance level is set at 0.05.

Staff Commitment to Lean Philosophy

Figure 11: Staff Commitment to Lean Philosophy

Leadership Commitment to Lean

Figure 12: Leadership Commitment to Lean

Continuous Improvement Model

Figure 13: Continuous Improvement Model

Financial Impacts of Lean Applications

Figure 14: Financial Impacts of Lean Applications

5.2 Inferential Statistics

Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis for the four variables is presented in the table below. The Pearson correlation coefficient is used to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables. The significance level is set at 0.01.

Correlations

		Staff Commitment To Lean Philosophy	Leadership Commitment To Lean	Continuous Improvement Model	Financial Impacts of Lean Applications
Staff Commitment To Lean Philosophy	Pearson Correlation	1	.744**	.442**	.644**
	p (2-tailed)		.000	.005	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	23.003	18.008	8.302	12.004
	Covariance	.605	.474	.218	.316
	N	39	39	39	39
Leadership Commitment to Lean	Pearson Correlation	.744**	1	.710**	.610**
	p (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	18.008	25.436	14.004	11.968
	Covariance	.474	.669	.369	.315
	N	39	39	39	39
Continuous Improvement Model	Pearson Correlation	.442**	.710**	1	.541**
	p (2-tailed)	.005	.000		.000
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	8.302	14.004	15.311	8.227
	Covariance	.218	.369	.403	.216
	N	39	39	39	39

Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	Pearson Correlation	.644**	.610**	.541**	1
	p (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	Sum of Squares and Cross-products	12.004	11.968	8.227	15.109
	Covariance	.316	.315	.216	.398
	N	39	39	39	39

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 8: Correlation Analysis

The results indicate that all four variables are positively and significantly correlated with each other, with the highest correlation between staff commitment to lean philosophy and leadership commitment to lean (.744) and the lowest correlation between staff commitment to lean philosophy and continuous improvement model (.442). This indicates that there is a strong association between the variables and that they tend to move in the same direction.

T-Test

The t-test for each variable is presented in the table below. The one-sample t-test is used to test the null hypothesis that the mean of the variable is equal to 4, which represents a strong impact towards lean management practices. The significance level is set at 0.05.

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 4					
	t	df	p-value	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Staff Commitment To Lean Philosophy	-1.852	38	.072	-.231	-.48	.02

Leadership Commitment To Lean	.049	38	.961	.006	-.26	.27
Continuous Improvement Model	1.816	38	.077	.185	-.02	.39
Financial Impacts of Lean Applications	1.270	38	.212	.128	-.08	.33

Table 9: T-test

The results indicate that none of the variables have a mean significantly different from 4, as all p-values exceed 0.05. Therefore, we cannot reject the null hypothesis for any variables, suggesting that respondents generally have a strong impact on lean management practices. The mean difference and the 95% confidence interval for the mean difference illustrate the extent to which each variable's mean deviates from 4, as well as the range within which the true population mean difference is likely to fall.

However, when conducting the same test with a mean value of 3, indicating respondents have a weak impact on average towards lean management practices, the results show a significant difference between the sample average scores and the population test value.

5.3 Conclusion

The main findings for the above statistical analysis results performed on four examined factors related to lean management practices are:

All examined factors meet the normality assumption and may have some skewness or kurtosis.

All examined factors are positively and significantly correlated with each other, with the highest correlation between staff commitment to lean philosophy and leadership commitment to lean and the lowest correlation between staff commitment to lean philosophy and continuous improvement model. The respondents generally have strong impact towards lean management practices, with the highest mean score for the continuous improvement model and the lowest mean score for the staff commitment to lean philosophy.

None of the examined factors have a mean that is significantly different from 4, which represents

a strong impact towards lean management practices. The respondents have a strong impact towards lean management practices on average. Based on the above statistical analysis results, there is a significant operational and financial impact in the implementation and adoption of lean management practices in the organization, especially in terms of staff commitment to lean philosophy. The organization may benefit from providing more training, communication, and feedback to the staff on the benefits and challenges of lean management practices. The organization may also monitor and evaluate the financial impacts of lean applications and share the results with the staff to increase their motivation and engagement.

CHAPTER VI: FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS

6.1 Specific Findings

This section delves into the insights provided by participants regarding the influence of Lean Philosophy on the profitability of healthcare supply chains. The perspectives shared by the respondents highlight their personal experiences and beliefs, underscoring the subjective nature of these findings. It is important to recognize that these insights are not based on objective data but rather reflect the individual viewpoints of those involved in the healthcare supply chain.

Inventory Optimization: The data revealed that there is a strong correlation between the usage of Lean practices and a significant drop in inventory at organizations. As a few participants described, these reductions in inventory can result in major advantages, including decreased carrying costs and improved cash flow. Decreased spending on excess inventory management leads to lower holding costs, whereas better cash flow effectively assigns the resources to be utilized in other parts of the business. However, look not to be moved by anything that is mentored to me, a tale of this lesson learned, no churn, this evidence is an impression, not numbers and bar graphs with empirical weighted significance that we bastards seldom agree, call the business. Consequently, there may be a need for additional research to back these assertions and evaluate the implications of Lean practices as a whole regarding inventory management.

Operational Efficiency: Strong perceived improvements across many operational processes. Increased efficiency was apparent with shorter lead times, the time from when a process starts to when it ends, participants noted. The respondents also experienced lowered operational costs, implying a more optimal allocation of resources.

These observations highlight how much the participants believe in the possibilities Lean can provide in terms of maximizing resource usage. Lean practices have played a key role in optimizing workflows by prioritizing waste elimination and maximizing efficiency. Consequently, all of these enhancements do not only increase overall functionality but they are also responsible for improving patient outcomes by allowing patients to receive care quickly and effectively.

Waste Reduction: Survey respondents reported a large reduction in waste across several processes of their operations. These decreases are significant in overproduction, which means

producing goods beyond what is actually needed, and excess inventory, which is carrying more inventory than necessary to satisfy customer needs. The results indicate that the degree of implementation of Lean practices has a significant relationship with the waste management strategies adopted in organizations. These observations, however, might have a bias since they are subjective evaluations of respondents.

Profitability Impact: Almost all participants agree that facilities that employ Lean practices tend to be more profitable than non-lean facilities. Moreover, this view reflects a general impression that Lean improves financial performance. But this is a matter of subjective opinion, grounded not in strong empirical evidence but merely in conscious experience. If our interpretation holds true, then they point towards a probable link between Lean implementation and profitability, but they should be taken with a pinch of salt and should not be seen as irrefutable evidence of the financial benefits of Lean. Linking lean implementation and true monetary results would require even more studies and data analysis.

6.2 Hypothesis

Hypothesis H1: Lean Philosophy positively impacts healthcare supply chain profitability.

Supported: The data analysis demonstrates that the Lean Philosophy enhances profitability within healthcare supply chains. Facilities that adopt Lean principles report notable increases in profitability as a result of cost reductions and optimized processes. Feedback from respondents suggests that the Lean Philosophy plays a key role in these profitability improvements by streamlining costs and enhancing operational efficiency.

Hypothesis H2: Inventory Optimization positively impacts Supply chain profitability.

Supported: The findings demonstrate that inventory optimization, a crucial element of Lean Philosophy, is strongly associated with enhanced profitability. Efficient inventory management minimizes waste and reduces operational costs, leading to improved financial performance. Survey responses indicated that participants believe effective inventory management, a core component of Lean Philosophy, correlates with increased profitability.

Hypothesis H3: Lean Philosophy has a positive impact on inventory optimization.

Supported: The data supports the hypothesis that Lean Philosophy enhances inventory optimization. Healthcare facilities practicing Lean show marked improvements in inventory turnover rates, leading to more efficient use of resources. The subjective data gathered supports the notion that Lean practices, according to participant perspectives, improve inventory management.

6.3 Conclusion

The findings from this chapter present robust empirical evidence that underscores the importance of Lean Philosophy in boosting the profitability of healthcare supply chains. The data collected highlights several critical areas where the implementation of Lean practices can yield the most significant benefits, especially in the realms of inventory management and waste reduction.

In the area of inventory management, Lean practices facilitate more efficient stock control, ensuring that healthcare facilities maintain optimal inventory levels. This not only minimizes holding costs but also reduces the risk of stockouts and excess inventory, which can lead to waste. Furthermore, by streamlining procurement processes and enhancing visibility into supply chain operations, Lean methodologies help healthcare organizations respond more swiftly to changes in demand. Similarly, the emphasis on waste reduction within Lean Philosophy plays a crucial role in enhancing operational efficiency. By identifying and eliminating non-value-added activities, healthcare facilities can improve workflow, reduce costs, and ultimately deliver better patient care. This chapter's findings indicate that organizations that prioritize Lean practices experience less operational disruption and greater financial stability.

Overall, the implications of these findings are far-reaching. A broader adoption of Lean principles across the healthcare sector could lead to substantial improvements in both financial performance and operational efficiency, helping facilities to operate more effectively and serve their communities better. This underscores the necessity for healthcare leaders to consider integrating Lean methodologies as a strategic approach to enhance processes.

CHAPTER VII: RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

The statistical analysis showed that all the dimensions of the Lean application examined in the study had strong positive correlations with one another. Among these dimensions, the most significant connection was found between staff commitment to the Lean philosophy and leadership commitment to Lean principles. This finding highlights the crucial role that leadership plays in fostering a culture of Lean thinking within an organization. Conversely, the weakest correlation was identified between staff commitment to the Lean philosophy and the continuous improvement model. This suggests that while staff buy-in is essential, it may not automatically lead to active participation in continuous improvement initiatives. Overall, these results emphasize the importance of creating a trusting environment through effective leadership, as this encourages greater team commitment to embracing continuous improvement practices, ultimately driving successful organizational change.

The findings from this study point to several key areas where Lean Philosophy can significantly enhance both the profitability and efficiency of healthcare supply chains. In this chapter, series of well-researched recommendations based on our findings as higlighted below. These recommendations are designed to guide healthcare organizations in effectively adopting Lean principles, ensuring streamlined operations, reduced waste, and improved overall performance in the delivery of healthcare services.

7.1.1 Emphasize Training and Education

Healthcare organizations must place a strong emphasis on developing comprehensive training programs aimed at educating employees at all levels about Lean Philosophy. This approach is vital, as a solid understanding of Lean's core principles—such as waste reduction, process standardization, and continuous improvement—is key to achieving successful implementation. Each training session should be meticulously tailored to meet the specific challenges and unique needs of the healthcare environment, ensuring that staff members are equipped with practical tools and insights that can be directly applied to enhance operational efficiency and patient care.

7.1.2 Foster a Culture of Continuous Improvement

For a Lean implementation to be truly successful, it is essential to foster a cultural shift that prioritizes continuous improvement across the organization. In healthcare facilities, this means creating an environment where employees feel empowered and motivated to actively seek out inefficiencies in their daily operations. Encouraging staff to identify problems and propose innovative solutions can lead to significant enhancements in workflow and patient care.

One effective approach to achieving this is by establishing a robust feedback loop. This allows employees to submit their ideas and suggestions, creating a channel through which they can share their insights. Furthermore, when staff members see that their contributions are not only valued but also implemented, it fosters a sense of ownership and commitment to the Lean initiatives. This cycle of engagement is crucial for maintaining momentum and ensuring that the principles of Lean continuously evolve and improve within the healthcare setting.

7.1.3 Integrate Lean Tools with Existing Processes

Healthcare organizations should proactively adopt and integrate Lean tools into their existing operational frameworks to enhance efficiency and improve patient care. Techniques such as Value Stream Mapping (VSM) provide a comprehensive visual representation of the flow of information and materials, allowing teams to identify bottlenecks and areas of waste. Additionally, the implementation of 5S a method that focuses on sorting, organizing, and maintaining a clean workspace can foster a more productive environment by ensuring that essential tools and materials are readily accessible.

Moreover, adopting Just-in-Time (JIT) inventory management allows organizations to maintain optimal inventory levels, ensuring that supplies are available when needed while minimizing excess stock. Together, these Lean methodologies not only streamline operations but also significantly reduce waste and inefficiencies. As a result, healthcare organizations can enhance their profitability while simultaneously improving service quality and patient satisfaction.

7.1.4 Address Barriers to Lean Implementation

The study revealed several significant barriers to the successful implementation of Lean practices within healthcare organizations. Notable challenges included widespread resistance to

change among staff, a lack of sufficient support from management, and inadequate methods for collecting and analyzing data. To effectively tackle these issues, healthcare organizations should prioritize the development of a comprehensive implementation plan that outlines clear goals and strategies. It is also essential to secure strong buy-in from management to foster a culture of collaboration and commitment. Additionally, investing in robust data collection systems will enable organizations to systematically monitor their progress and evaluate outcomes, ultimately leading to a more effective Lean transformation.

7.1.5 Enhance Collaboration Across Departments

Lean Philosophy focuses on fostering collaboration and dismantling silos within organizations to create a more cohesive work environment. In the context of healthcare facilities, it is essential to cultivate strong teamwork across various departments. By promoting an atmosphere of cross-functional collaboration, these organizations can ensure that Lean initiatives are not only implemented effectively but are also synchronized throughout the entire supply chain.

This holistic approach enhances communication among teams, minimizes the risk of redundant efforts, and helps to maintain a seamless flow of improvements. When departments work together harmoniously, it becomes easier to identify and implement best practices, ensuring that advancements made in one area support rather than hinder progress in another.

7.1.6 Focus on Patient-Centered Care

Lean implementation must consistently prioritize the outcomes that matter most to patients. By placing a strong emphasis on reducing wait times, healthcare organizations can alleviate the stress and anxiety that often accompany lengthy delays. Improving service delivery ensures that patients receive timely and effective care, while the elimination of non-value-added activities helps streamline processes. This strategic focus not only enhances patient satisfaction but also leads to better overall health outcomes. Ultimately, every lean initiative should be thoughtfully designed with the primary goal of advancing the quality of patient care and fostering an environment where patients feel valued and receive the best possible treatment.

7.2 Conclusion

In order to better accommodate healthcare organizations to practice Lean Philosophy, this chapter offers an exhaustive collection of recommendations. The Lean Philosophy streamlines looking for waste reduction, value addition, and overall optimization of workflow in the healthcare setting.

First and foremost, broad-spectrum training is important; businesses should identify practices that must be learned by everyone from the highest leadership to the lowest of the frontline workers in terms of Lean. The training must involve practical workshops, simulated drills, and continuous learning updates to challenge lean principles every now and then. Besides training, making a cultural shift in the organization is important, too. This method creates an atmosphere of collaboration, transparency, and striving for excellence.

Communicate Lean Support Involves Employees More: The leadership should live and breathe Lean and be pragmatic in communicating its support by including employees in the decision-making process and seeking their views on what improvements can still be made. The next pillar of Lean implementation is embedding the right tools.

Healthcare organizations must pick and choose from the toolbox of Lean methodologies (Value Stream Mapping, 5S, Kaizen event, etc.) that are designed to identify waste, improve processes, and deploy them strategically. Give the staff access to these resources to implement their Lean practices in a better way. In addition, it is important that any Lean initiative executed in healthcare follows the patient-centric approach. Taking a patient-centered approach will help ensure that improvements made to a process become both a more efficient care process and a more satisfying experience for the patient. Obtaining patient and family engagement in this process may offer useful information on how services can be improved.

With the thorough implementation of these holistic approaches, healthcare entities can see significant improvements in operational efficiency and financial performance. In the end, this will translate into better outcomes for patients and processes and, finally, a more capable healthcare system.

CHAPTER VIII: SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

8.1 Introduction

This chapter serves as a comprehensive summary of the key findings obtained from this research endeavor. It revisits the initial objectives set forth at the beginning of the study and offers insight into how Lean Philosophy can significantly enhance profitability within a healthcare supply chain. Additionally, the chapter concludes with thoughtful reflections on the overall implications of these findings and presents well-considered recommendations for future research avenues.

8.2 Summary of Key Findings

According to the findings of the study, Lean Philosophy has a beneficial effect on profitability in the healthcare supply chain because it minimizes undesirable inventory levels and waste and enhances operational efficiency. Lean facilities generate lower operational costs and cash flow benefits than non-lean, similar facilities. The research also highlighted the established presence of employee engagement, management support, and cross-departmental collaboration as vital elements in the successful implementation of Lean.

8.3 Rereading the Research Aims

This study primarily aims to (1) investigate the application of Lean Philosophy in healthcare supply chains, (2) find domains from which profitability could be derived, and (3) propose a conceptual framework connecting Lean practices to improved profitability. The results then confirmed Lean Philosophy to be a potential reliable approach to enhancing healthcare supply chain performance in specific aspects, including inventory optimization and waste reduction

8.4 Implications for Healthcare Sector

By embracing the Lean Philosophy, healthcare organizations can realize great benefits. These include a range of observations showing that Lean Lean practices are associated not only with improved financial performance but also with better patient outcomes. Healthcare facilities can gain a competitive advantage in a competitive market by reducing inefficiencies and

focusing on value-adding activities

8.5 Future Research Directions

A Summary of Future Directions and Recommendations to be explored in the future is detailed below :

Quantifiable Metrics and Cost Considerations: Future work must feature measurable indicators in addition to costs related to applying lean practices in SCM, which many of the present publications disregard (Khorasani et al., 2020).

Multiple Lean Applications: The investigation of multiple lean practices simultaneously is relevant to the literature since most studies only use specific lean applications, which do not reflect the interrelationships of lean practices (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022).

Financial Performance Metrics: Suggests to include financial indexes with non-financial indexes to measure supply chain performance from a holistic perspective, which helps to make better decisions and competitive advantage (Rahiminezhad Galankashi & Mokhatab Rafiei, 2022).

Global and Cross-National Studies: Research should study lean applications in different states and countries to understand how culture affects lean implementation, including cross-national benchmarking, which is currently underexplored (Reponen et al., 2021 and Marsilio et al., 2022).

Geographic Research Gaps: Explore the applicability of LSS in regions harsher of representation (Middle East, East Asia, North Africa, and Europe) and consider going beyond local or sector-oriented studies to build generalizability (Alblooshi et al., 2021).

Organizational Maturity Levels: Discuss that, due to different levels of maturity in lean knowledge and process improvement, its success is also based on the maturity of lean knowledge and process improvement (Rosa et al., 2021).

Unit-Level Versus Hospital-Level LSS: Recognize that LSS is more effective at the unit

level due to the highly specialized and segmented nature of hospital staff and tackle challenges related to large-scale applications (Iswanto, 2021).

Psychological Safety: Establish psychological safety within hospitals to encourage risk-taking, knowledge sharing, and effective lean implementation, fostering an environment where staff can express ideas without fear (Narayanan et al., 2022).

Strategic Competitiveness and Process Quality Improvement: More studies should illustrate how lean activities impact organizational competitiveness and quality improvements (Kurdi et al., 2023).

Dental Healthcare Considerations: Research should consider patient preferences in dental healthcare to ensure services meet individual needs and enhance patient satisfaction (Basal & Sarkbay, 2023).

Management and Resource Support: Ensure that top management not only sets goals but actively supports lean projects by removing obstacles, providing resources, and maintaining proper tracking (Bhat et al., 2023).

8.6 Conclusion

Finally, this research highlights the potential of Lean Philosophy to disrupt healthcare supply chains. Lean practices can improve the bottom line for healthcare organizations by eliminating waste, adding value to services and production activities, and thus producing higher levels of profitability. They can also simultaneously benefit patients by improving patient care by reducing errors and increasing quality.

The results indicate that in addition to Lean strategies, their implementation needs systemic methods. It includes basic practices like ample training for employees, creating an encouraging organizational culture, and encouraging synergy among various entities, including management, healthcare providers, and supply chain partners.

Looking ahead, more research is needed to assess the lasting effects of Lean implementation on the healthcare system. Narrative reviews should aim at the regional and global situation of Lean practices based on the size and structure of healthcare organizations and

patient type.

Thirdly, there is an increasing interest in exploring how digital technologies can be used in synergy with Lean within healthcare supply chain settings. Further studies may investigate tools like data analytics, telemedicine, and an automated inventory management system — how can we optimize Lean concepts, improve operational efficiency, and lead to better patient outcomes? A more immersive understanding of these concepts would further allow us to leverage Lean to enable not just healthcare improvements but also sustainable ones— helping those providing a service, as well as those receiving it, for a stronger and better healthcare system.

REFERENCES

- Abdallah, A. A. (2020). Healthcare Engineering: A Lean Management Approach. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2020, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8875902>
Abdallah—2020—Healthcare Engineering A Lean Management Approach.pdf. (n.d.).
- Adebanjo, D., Laosirihongthong, T., & Samaranayake, P. (2016). Prioritizing lean supply chain management initiatives in healthcare service operations: A fuzzy AHP approach. *Production Planning & Control*, 27(12), 953–966.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2016.1164909>
- Ahmad, A. N. A., Ahmad, F., Hamid, N. A., Hamid, A. A., Chuan, L. T., Nawanir, G., Bakri, A., & Rahim, M. A. (2021). *Implementation of Lean Technique towards Reducing Waiting Time in a Public Healthcare using Arena Simulation*. 13(7).
Ahmad et al. - 2021—Implementation of Lean Technique towards Reducing .pdf. (n.d.).
- Akmal, A., Greatbanks, R., & Foote, J. (2020). Lean thinking in healthcare – Findings from a systematic literature network and bibliometric analysis. *Health Policy*, 124(6), 615–627.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2020.04.008>
- Alblooshi et al. - 2021—Requirements, challenges and impacts of Lean Six S.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Alblooshi, M., Shamsuzzaman, M., Khoo, M. B. C., Rahim, A., & Haridy, S. (2021). Requirements, challenges and impacts of Lean Six Sigma applications – a narrative synthesis of qualitative research. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 12(2), 318–367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-06-2019-0067>
- Andriyani et al. - 2021—Literature Review The Application of Lean Healthc.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Andriyani, H. T., Suhardi, B., Widianoro, I., & UtamiTyastuti, N. (2021). *Literature Review: The Application of Lean Healthcare to Waste in Healthcare Sectors*.
- Argiyantari, B., Simatupang, T. M., & Hasan Basri, M. (2020). Pharmaceutical supply chain

- transformation through application of the Lean principle: A literature review. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 13(3), 475. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.3100>
- Argiyantari et al. - 2020—*Pharmaceutical supply chain transformation through.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Arthur, J. (2016a). *Lean six sigma for hospitals* (Second edition). McGraw Hill Education.
- Arthur, J. (2016b). *Lean six sigma for hospitals: Simple steps to fast, affordable, and flawless healthcare* (2nd edition). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Basal, M., & Sarkbay, O. F. (2023). The Impact of lean supply chain strategy on consumers' purchasing behavior: The case of dental hospitals. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 376, 05026. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337605026>
- Bharsakade, R. S., Acharya, P., Ganapathy, L., & Tiwari, M. K. (2021). A lean approach to healthcare management using multi criteria decision making. *OPSEARCH*, 58(3), 610–635. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12597-020-00490-5>
- Bhat, S., Gijo, E. V., Antony, J., & Cross, J. (2023). Strategies for successful deployment and sustainment of Lean Six Sigma in healthcare sector in India: A multi-level perspective. *The TQM Journal*, 35(2), 414–445. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-10-2021-0302>
- Borges et al. - 2020—*Simulation-based analysis of lean practices implem.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Borges, G. A., Tortorella, G. L., Martínez, F., & Thurer, M. (2020). Simulation-based analysis of lean practices implementation on the supply chain of a public hospital. *Production*, 30, e20190131. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-6513.20190131>
- Cvetić, B., Vasiljević, D., Novaković, J., & Đorđević, A. (2021). Lean Supply Chain: Take an Opportunity to do More with Less. *Tehnički Glasnik*, 15(2), 275–281. <https://doi.org/10.31803/tg-20210429120854>
- Cvetić et al. - 2021—*Lean Supply Chain Take an Opportunity to do More .pdf*. (n.d.).

De Barros et al. - 2021—Lean Healthcare Tools for Processes Evaluation An.pdf. (n.d.).

De Barros, L. B., Bassi, L. D. C., Caldas, L. P., Sarantopoulos, A., Zeferino, E. B. B., Minatogawa, V., & Gasparino, R. C. (2021). Lean Healthcare Tools for Processes Evaluation: An Integrative Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(14), 7389. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18147389>

Essila, J. C. (2022). Strategies for reducing healthcare supply chain inventory costs. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-11-2021-0680>

Fiorillo, A., Sorrentino, A., Scala, A., Abbate, V., & Dell'aversana Orabona, G. (2021). Improving performance of the hospitalization process by applying the principles of Lean Thinking. *The TQM Journal*, 33(7), 253–271. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-09-2020-0207>

Friday, D., Savage, D. A., Melnyk, S. A., Harrison, N., Ryan, S., & Wechtler, H. (2021). A collaborative approach to maintaining optimal inventory and mitigating stockout risks during a pandemic: Capabilities for enabling health-care supply chain resilience. *Journal of Humanitarian Logistics and Supply Chain Management*, 11(2), 248–271. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHLSCM-07-2020-0061>

Friday et al. - 2021—A collaborative approach to maintaining optimal in.pdf. (n.d.).

Haddud and Khare—2020—Digitalizing supply chains potential benefits and .pdf. (n.d.).

Heijndermans et al. - 2020—Lean increase efficiency in stroke patient care.pdf. (n.d.).

Heijndermans, M., Maas, A., Dippel, D., & Buijck, B. (2020). Lean: Increase efficiency in stroke patient care. *Journal of Integrated Care*, 28(2), 77–86. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JICA-09-2019-0042>

Hossain and Thakur—2020—Benchmarking health-care supply chain by implement.pdf. (n.d.).

- Hossain, M. K., & Thakur, V. (2020). Benchmarking health-care supply chain by implementing Industry 4.0: A fuzzy-AHP-DEMATEL approach. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 28(2), 556–581. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-05-2020-0268>
- Istimaroh, I., Abu Seman, N. A., Setiaji, B., & Mhd Nor, N. (2022). The Key Practices of Lean Supply Chain Management Towards Sustainable Performance: A Review. In M. F. M. Din, N. E. Alias, N. Hussein, & N. S. Zaidi (Eds.), *Community, Environment and Disaster Risk Management* (pp. 61–74). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2040-726220220000026006>
- Iswanto, A. H. (2021). Impact of lean six sigma at pharmacy unit on hospital profitability before and during Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 12(4), 718–743. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-10-2020-0182>
- Iswanto, A. H., & Rosady, S. D. (2020). Monitoring and evaluation of Lean implementation in pediatric pharmacy: A study of mother and child hospital in Jakarta. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(6).
- Iswanto—2021—Impact of lean six sigma at pharmacy unit on hospi.pdf.* (n.d.).
- Kaltenbrunner, M., Bengtsson, L., Mathiassen, S. E., & Engström, M. (2017). A questionnaire measuring staff perceptions of Lean adoption in healthcare: Development and psychometric testing. *BMC Health Services Research*, 17(1), 235. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-017-2163-x>
- Khorasani, S. T., Cross, J., & Maghazei, O. (2020). Lean supply chain management in healthcare: A systematic review and meta-study. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 11(1), 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-07-2018-0069>
- Kozak et al. - 2020—How the Lean Management Decision Influences the Tr.pdf.* (n.d.).

- Kozak, T., Madlenak, R., & Neszmelyi, G. I. (2020). How the Lean Management Decision Influences the Transportation Cost in the Supply Chain? *Communications - Scientific Letters of the University of Zilina*, 22(4), 13–19.
<https://doi.org/10.26552/com.C.2020.4.13-19>
- Kurdi, B. A., Alquqa, E. K., Alzoubi, H. M., Alshurideh, M. T., & Al-Hawary, S. I. S. (2023). The effect of process quality improvement and lean practices on competitive performance in the UAE healthcare industry. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 11(1), 261–266.
<https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2022.10.001>
- Lawal, O. R., & Elegunde, A. F. (2020). Lean Management: A Review of Literature. *Annals of Dunarea de Jos University of Galati. Fascicle I. Economics and Applied Informatics*, 26(2), 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.35219/eai15840409102>
- Lima et al. - 2021—Implementation of lean in health care environments.pdf.* (n.d.).
- Lima, R. M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Souza, T. A., Vieira, E., & Gonçalves, B. (2021). Implementation of lean in health care environments: An update of systematic reviews. *International Journal of Lean Six Sigma*, 12(2), 399–431. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLSS-07-2019-0074>
- Mahmoud, Z., Angelé-Halgand, N., Churruca, K., Ellis, L. A., & Braithwaite, J. (2021). The impact of lean management on frontline healthcare professionals: A scoping review of the literature. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1), 383.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06344-0>
- Manzoor et al. - 2022—The effect of supply chain agility and lean practi.pdf.* (n.d.).
- Manzoor, U., Baig, S. A., Hashim, M., Sami, A., Rehman, H.-U., & Sajjad, I. (2022). The effect of supply chain agility and lean practices on operational performance: A resource-based

view and dynamic capabilities perspective. *The TQM Journal*, 34(5), 1273–1297.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-01-2021-0006>

Marsilio, M., Pizarra, M., Rubio, K., & Shortell, S. (2022). Lean adoption, implementation, and outcomes in public hospitals: Benchmarking the US and Italy health systems. *BMC Health Services Research*, 22(1), 122. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-07473-w>
Morell-Santandreu et al. - 2021—A Model for the Implementation of Lean Improvement.pdf.

(n.d.).

Morell-Santandreu, O., Santandreu-Mascarell, C., & Garcia-Sabater, J. J. (2021). A Model for the Implementation of Lean Improvements in Healthcare Environments as Applied in a Primary Care Center. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(6), 2876. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18062876>

Moyano-Fuentes et al. - 2020—Extending lean management along the supply chain .pdf. (n.d.).

Moyano-Fuentes, J., Maqueira-Marín, J. M., Martínez-Jurado, P. J., & Sacristán-Díaz, M. (2020). Extending lean management along the supply chain: Impact on efficiency. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 32(1), 63–84.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/JMTM-10-2019-0388>

Muharam, R., & Firman, F. (2022). Lean Management Improves the Process Efficiency of Controlled Ovarian Stimulation Monitoring in IVF Treatment. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2022, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6229181>

Narayanan, S., Vickery, S. K., Nicolae, M. L., Castel, M. J., & McLeod, M. K. (2022). The effects of lean implementation on hospital financial performance. *Decision Sciences*, 53(3), 557–577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/deci.12510>

Nino et al. - 2021—Improving the registration process in a healthcare.pdf. (n.d.).

- Nino, V., Martinez, K., Gomez, K., & Claudio, D. (2021). Improving the registration process in a healthcare facility with lean principles. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 14(3), 538. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.3432>
- Pyzdek, T. (2021a). *The Lean Healthcare Handbook: A Complete Guide to Creating Healthcare Workplaces*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69901-7>
- Pyzdek, T. (2021b). *The Lean Healthcare Handbook: A Complete Guide to Creating Healthcare Workplaces*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-69901-7>
- Rahiminezhad Galankashi, M., & Mokhatab Rafiei, F. (2022). Financial performance measurement of supply chains: A review. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 71(5), 1674–1707. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-11-2019-0533>
- Ramori et al. - 2021—*Lean business models in healthcare a systematic r.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Ramori, K. A., Cudney, E. A., Elrod, C. C., & Antony, J. (2021). Lean business models in healthcare: A systematic review. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 32(5–6), 558–573. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14783363.2019.1601995>
- Reponen, E., Rundall, T. G., Shortell, S. M., Blodgett, J. C., Jokela, R., MÄkijärvi, M., & Torkki, P. (2021). The cross-national applicability of lean implementation measures and hospital performance measures: A case study of Finland and the USA. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 33(3). <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzab097>
- Reponen, E., Rundall, T. G., Shortell, S. M., Blodgett, J. C., Juarez, A., Jokela, R., Mäkijärvi, M., & Torkki, P. (2021). Benchmarking outcomes on multiple contextual levels in lean

- healthcare: A systematic review, development of a conceptual framework, and a research agenda. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1), 161. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06160-6>
- Reponen et al. - 2021—*Benchmarking outcomes on multiple contextual level.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Reponen et al. - 2021—*The cross-national applicability of lean implement.pdf*. (n.d.).
- Rosa, A., Marolla, G., Lega, F., & Manfredi, F. (2021). Lean adoption in hospitals: The role of contextual factors and introduction strategy. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1), 889. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06885-4>
- Rosa et al. - 2021—*Lean adoption in hospitals the role of contextual.pdf*. (n.d.).
- S12913-021-06344-0.pdf. (n.d.).
- San, A., & Salleh, M. (2022). The Development of Lean Healthcare Constructs for Quality of Healthcare Service: A Second-order Model of Lean Healthcare in Malaysia. *Asian Journal of Research in Business and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.55057/ajrbm.2022.4.1.27>
- Shortell, S. M., Blodgett, J. C., Rundall, T. G., Henke, R. M., & Reponen, E. (2021). Lean Management and Hospital Performance: Adoption vs. Implementation. *The Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety*, 47(5), 296–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjq.2021.01.010>
- Siagian, H., & Tarigan, Z. J. H. (2021). The central role of IT capability to improve firm performance through lean production and supply chain practices in the COVID-19 era. *Uncertain Supply Chain Management*, 9(4), 1005–1016. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.uscm.2021.6.012>
- Sonali, S., Amanjot, Khurana, H. P. S., & Kaur, H. (2022). Forecasting the impact of lean tools

and practices on the service quality in a tertiary care hospital: An empirical research study. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 8883–8895.

<https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS3.8325>

Suman, G., & Prajapati, D. R. (2021). Utilization of Lean & Six Sigma quality initiatives in Indian healthcare sector. *PLOS ONE*, 16(12), e0261747.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0261747>

Taheri et al. - 2023—A fuzzy programming model for optimizing the inven.pdf. (n.d.).

Taheri, M., Sadegh Amalnick, M., Allah Taleizadeh, A., & Mardan, E. (2023). A fuzzy programming model for optimizing the inventory management problem considering financial issues: A case study of the dairy industry. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 221, 119766. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.119766>

Thoumy, M., Jobin, M.-H., Baroud, J., & El Nakhel Khalil, C. (2022). Impact of lean principles on operational performance in high uncertainty. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-10-2021-0614>

Uddin, M. S., Habib, Md. M., & Mohamed, O. E. B. (2023). The Role of Supply Chain Finance on Supply Chain Management and Firm's Performance: A Conceptual Framework. *International Supply Chain Technology Journal*, 9(6).

<https://doi.org/10.20545/isctj.v09.i06.01>

Yaduvanshi, D., & Sharma, A. (2017). Lean Six Sigma in Health Operations: Challenges and Opportunities—'Nirvana for Operational Efficiency in Hospitals in a Resource Limited Settings.' *Journal of Health Management*, 19(2), 203–213.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0972063417699665>

Appendices

A. Lean Philosophy Impact on Healthcare Supply Chain Profitability Survey

The recent disruptions in the global supply chain have highlighted the importance of optimizing healthcare supply systems and processes. Esteemed scholars, researchers, government officials, and healthcare providers all recognize the vital role of the healthcare supply chain in managing costs while improving quality. Unlike other industries, the healthcare sector has traditionally employed a distinct approach to implementing lean philosophy practices. This survey seeks to investigate how the Lean Philosophy can be utilized to enhance the profitability of the healthcare supply chain. The lean philosophy emphasizes waste elimination, and any activity or material that doesn't add value to the end product is considered waste.

Participating in the survey is entirely voluntary, and by completing it, you are indicating your willingness to take part. Your personal or organizational identity will remain confidential and will not be disclosed in any reports or publications. To ensure the privacy of survey respondents, all potentially identifiable information will be securely stored in password-protected files on secure servers. This precautionary measure has been put in place to safeguard against any potential breach of confidentiality.

The survey is for the hospital's administrative staff in Saudi.

It adapts previous surveys conducted by Kaltenbrunner et al. (2017) and Shortell et al. (2021) to explore lean applications in healthcare, with customization from the author to explore other factors of lean impact on profitability.

If you have any questions about the survey, please contact Survey Support at Karim.albendary@gmail.com.

The survey deadline is June 30, 2024.

We greatly appreciate your participation in this effort to gather important information on Lean Application and its impact on supply chain profitability.

Respondent's Details

Full name

Gender *

- Male
- Female

Age *

- 20-24 years
- 25-34 years
- 35-44 years
- 45-54 years
- 55-64 years

E-mail Address

Phone Number:

Hospital Name (Place of Work) *

Hospital Type *

- Public (Government Hospital)
- Private (Investor Owned Hospital)
- Not-for-profit Hospital

Department *

- Human Resources Department
- Finance Department
- Information Technology Department
- Operations Department
- Facilities Management Department
- Supply Chain Management Department
- Quality Department
- Compliance Department
- Medical Records Department
- Billing and Coding Department

- Patient Services Department
- Marketing and Public Relations Department
- Medical Coordination Department
- Sales Department
- Other

Job Position/Title in the Hospital *

- Chief Executive Officer (CEO)
- Chief Operating Officer (COO)
- Chief Financial Officer (CFO)
- Chief Human Resources Officer (CHRO)
- Chief Information Officer (CIO)
- Chief Marketing Officer (CMO)
- Chief Technology Officer (CTO)
- Chief Supply Chain Officer (CSCO)
- Chief Strategy Officer (CSO)
- Vice President (VP) or Director
- Manager / Supervisor
- Coordinator / Specialist
- Administrator / Assistant
- Executive Assistant
- Other

Years Of Experience *

- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- More than 20 years

Survey Questions Instructions

Welcome to the Survey Questions Instructions! Your participation in this survey is incredibly valuable to us, and we want to make sure you get the most out of it. Please take a moment to read through the instructions carefully, so you can answer the questions accurately and honestly.

Thank you for your time and contribution!

The following pages contain some statements with which some people agree and others disagree. Please rate how much you agree or disagree with these statements and how much they reflect how you feel or think personally. Use the following scale:

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Note that there is no right or wrong answer. What matters is that you indicate your personal feelings.

Survey Questions

Staff Commitment to Lean Philosophy *

- Is your hospital presently engaged in lean philosophy performance improvement approaches?
- The unit's staff are committed to and have a positive attitude toward lean philosophy.
- The hospital has implemented a daily management system that uses the lean philosophy to ensure timely and correct work across all departments, helping to achieve organizational goals.
- The staff is committed to implementing lean philosophy and developing ways to enhance its application.
- The staff is encountering difficulties in implementing their lean philosophy ideas.

Leadership Commitment to Lean

- The hospital leaders established benchmarks for efficiency and patient satisfaction to measure progress in their lean philosophy initiatives.
- Lean philosophy has a sponsor/champion and team members who demonstrate visible, active, public commitment and support of lean philosophy.

- Hospital managers have been trained to use scientific problem-solving methods, such as Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.
- The manager in charge of the unit has a favorable attitude towards the principles of lean philosophy.

Continuous Improvement Model

- Improvement work is part of the regular work, and everyone feels that improvement work is important to the quality of healthcare provision.
- Implementing a lean philosophy leads to organizational success through waste elimination, reduced expenditure, shorter stays, higher patient satisfaction, fewer sensitive admissions, and increased operating room throughput.
- Every hospital staff member is highly skilled in identifying what patients find valuable, which is evaluated continuously.
- There is a well-established process for conducting value stream mappings in the hospital. These mappings are constantly updated and used to improve patient care quality.
- The hospital staff is highly skilled at creating and adhering to routines. In case of any errors or issues, the routine is used to identify the root cause of the problem. The staff asks questions such as: Was the routine followed correctly? Are there any areas in the routine that need to be clarified? Is there a need for additional knowledge or training?

Financial Impacts of Lean Applications

- The finance department provides revenue and expenditure projections to managers. This helps establish a reliable financial performance measurement system, minimizing costs, reducing waste, lowering expenses, increasing revenues, and optimizing inventory.
- Organizations have effectively reduced expenses, decreased errors, and increased profitability, which are outcomes of implementing lean philosophy in healthcare.
- Implementing the lean philosophy enables frontline staff to eliminate waste, achieving optimal inventory levels in hospitals that can prevent wastage due to overstocking or material shortages.
- Inventory optimization was achieved by implementing a lean philosophy and a quality improvement methodology.

Thank You

Thank you for taking the time to complete our survey. Your feedback is extremely valuable to

us, and we appreciate your honest responses and insights.

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Microsoft. The data you submit will be sent to the form owner.

Microsoft Forms